

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D7.8 Report on legal and ethics monitoring

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUCO	European Council
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is deliverable D7.8 "Report on legal and ethics monitoring". This report is the result of activities carried out within work package WP7 and specifically task T7.4 "Legal framework, ethics and gender balance".

"Report on legal and ethics monitoring" provides an overview of the monitoring of legal and ethics principles, policies, procedures and processes in the 5G-ROUTES project.

The report outlines the legal and ethical framework related to the implementation of the 5G-ROUTES project. The possible impact of legal and ethical principles, policies, procedures, processes and related risks are also analysed.

In Chapter 2, the document provides an overview and analyses the legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to the project. The focus is on legislation, regulations, rules and procedures in the following areas:

- research and development;
- human rights;
- artificial intelligence;
- data processing, protection and privacy;
- cyber security;
- telecommunication.

Moreover, Chapter 2 summarizes the assessment of how legislation, regulations, rules and procedures were implemented in 5G-ROUTES.

In Chapter 3, the ethical principles, policies, procedures and processes of the project are outlined. In terms of ethics, the requirements and conditions in the ethics guidelines and recommendations and the corresponding principles, policies and procedures in the project are reviewed and analysed. Moreover, Chapter 3 summarizes the assessment of how ethical principles, policies, procedures and processes were implemented in 5G-ROUTES.

1 Introduction and scope

Document identifier and title. This document constitutes deliverable D7.8. The deliverable is titled “D7.8: Report on legal and ethics monitoring” v1.0. It is the result of the work conducted in work package WP7, Task T7.4 “Legal framework, ethics and gender balance”.

Purpose of the document. The preparation of this report considers the final assessment of possible legal and ethical concerns and issues related to the project and its activities.

The purpose of this document is to review, describe and analyse the principles, policies, procedures and processes implemented in the 5G-ROUTES project to highlight:

- research and development activities are legally and ethically sound;
- conducting research and development activities complies with legislation and ethical guidelines;
- research data is processed ethically in accordance with legislation;
- legislation in the field of human rights, artificial intelligence, cyber security, data protection and telecommunications has been taken into account;
- the privacy requirements of the research are legally and ethically met.

Legal topics. The report provides an overview, describes and analyses the legislation related to the project. The main focus is on the following European and national legislation related to the implementation of the project:

- research and development;
- human rights;
- artificial intelligence;
- privacy;
- data processing and protection;
- cyber security;
- telecommunication.

In the case of legislation, its impacts and risks on the activities of the research and development project are reviewed, described and analysed.

Ethics topics. In implementing the ethical principles of the 5G-ROUTES project, attention has been paid to the following ethical topics:

- the main ethical principles of research;
- ethical requirements for conducting scientific research;
- ethics of research data processing, including personal data processing and protection;
- ethical issues related to involving people in research, including privacy;
- ethical issues related to gender perspective, including equality;
- the main ethical impacts and risks of research.

Project outputs and document structure. The following sections present the outputs of the project with the different parts of this document and provide an overview of the document and its structure.

1.1 Project Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map the responsibilities of the 5G-ROUTES project, both within the formal deliverable and the task description, with the relevant outputs of the project and the work done in task T7.4, and documenting its potential results in this deliverable.

Table 1. Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions for Task T7.4 / Deliverable D7.8

5G-ROUTES Component Title	5G-ROUTES Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.8: Report on legal and ethics monitoring v1.0: Final report			
TASKS			
T7.4 “Legal framework, ethics and gender balance”	Research and development activities are legally and ethically sound.	Chapter 2 Chapter 3	The legal and ethical justification of research and development has been reviewed and analysed.
	Conducting research and development activities complies with legislation and ethical guidelines.	Chapter 2 Chapter 3	Compliance with the legislation and ethical guidelines for conducting research and development activities has been reviewed and analysed.
	Research data is processed ethically in accordance with legislation.	Chapter 3	The processing of research data ethically in accordance with legislation has been reviewed and analysed.
	Legislation in the field of telecommunications is considered.	Chapter 2	Legislation in the field of telecommunications has been considered.
	Research privacy requirements are followed legally and ethically.	Chapter 2 Chapter 3	The privacy requirements of the research are legally and ethically met.
	Reviewing, specifying and analysing the ethical requirements of the 5G-ROUTES research project.	Chapter 3	The ethical requirements of the 5G-ROUTES research project have been reviewed, specified and analysed.
	Development and implementation of ethical principles of the 5G-ROUTES research project.	Chapter 3	The ethical principles of the 5G-ROUTES research project have been developed and implemented. The ethical principles of 5G-ROUTES research are based on a legal and ethical background framework, including European Union definitions of research ethics on human beings’ involvement, detailed description of international ethics standards, legislations and codes of conduct. This aims to ensure the compliance of project

			activities from the legal and ethics perspectives.
	Designing and developing information and informed consent forms for solving ethical issues of the 5G-ROUTES research project.	Chapter 3 Annex II Annex III	Information and informed consent forms have been designed and developed to address the ethical issues of the 5G-ROUTES research project.
	Planning, reviewing and monitoring the principles for handling legal issues during the project's lifetime.	Chapter 2	The research activities of the project are planned, reviewed and monitored from a legal point of view.
	Formulation of principles of research ethics, which consist of guidelines and recommendations on how to address potential ethical and legal issues of the project.	Chapter 3	The principles of scientific ethics are formulated by preparing guidelines and recommendations on how to handle possible ethical and legal issues of the project.
	Designing legal and ethical principles of project activities to guide partners in their activities. Development of scientific ethics principles to be followed by 5G-ROUTES partners.	Chapter 2 Chapter 3 Annex I	Legal and ethical principles for project activities are designed to guide partners in their activities. Scientific ethics principles are developed for 5G-ROUTES partners to follow.
	During the project, attention is paid to gender balance, so that the ratio of women and men remains as balanced as possible among the people working in the project.	Chapter 3	5G-ROUTES' approach to gender balance follows the guidance on gender equality in Horizon 2020 as recommended by the European Commission.

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Following the introduction, the report structure is as follows:

Chapter 2 Research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures, including:

- European Union legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities;
- Establishment and implementation of the European Horizon 2020 – legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Fundamental human rights legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Artificial intelligence legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Cyber security legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Electronic communications legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Finnish research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Estonian research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Latvian research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- Data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities;
- European Union data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities;
- Finnish data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures legislation related to research, development and innovation activities;
- Estonian data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities;
- Latvian data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities;
- Moreover, Chapter 2 summarizes the assessment of how legislation, regulations, rules and procedures were implemented in 5G-ROUTES.

Chapter 3 Ethics principles, policies and procedures in research, development and innovation activities, including:

- European Union Horizon 2020 research ethics principles and policies;
- Ethics principles and rights, their adoption and application;
- Ethical requirements arising from the research activities of the 5G-ROUTES project;
- Ethical aspects of data processing, protection and privacy and their application;
- Personal data processing and protection requirements and implementation;
- General ethical aspects of scientific data processing and protection and their application;
- Ethical aspects of artificial intelligence;
- Gender perspective;

- Research ethics framework, principles and policies and their application;
- Ethics management safeguards, identification and mitigation of ethical risks and the tools used for this purpose;
- Moreover, Chapter 3 summarizes the assessment of how ethical principles, policies, procedures and processes were implemented in 5G-ROUTES.

Chapter 4 presents the conclusions and **Chapter 5** provides the references.

Annexes I to III complement main body of the report.

2 Research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

2.1 European Union legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities

Purpose of the chapter. The purpose of this chapter is to review, describe and analyse the legislation, regulations, rules and procedures implemented in the 5G-ROUTES project to highlight the following:

- research and development activities are legally justified;
- in the course of conducting research and development, attention is paid to legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- the processing of research data is based on the relevant legislation, regulations, rules and procedures;
- legislation, regulations, rules and procedures in the field of artificial intelligence, data protection, cyber security and telecommunications are taken into account.

Main goal and focus. The main goal is to focus on reviewing, describing and analysing legislation, regulations, rules and procedures affecting the activities of the 5G-ROUTES project. At the same time, the focus is on legislation that affects the ethics of conducting a research project, the corresponding principles and procedures. The main focus is on European and national legislation, regulations, rules and procedures in the following areas related to project implementation:

- Research, development and innovation activities;
- Establishment and implementation of the European Horizon 2020;
- Establishment and implementation of the European Horizon 2020 participation and dissemination;
- Fundamental human rights;
- Artificial intelligence;
- Cyber security;
- Electronic communications;
- Data management and protection of personal data;
- Privacy.

In the case of the aforementioned legislation, regulations, rules and procedures, their potential impacts and risks on the activities of the research and development project are reviewed, described and analysed.

2.1.1 Establishment and implementation of the European Horizon 2020 – legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Legislation related to the establishment and implementation of the European Horizon 2020. When conducting European research, development and innovation activities, it is important to follow the legislation underlying European Commission projects. The awareness of the members who performed the administration activities of the 5G-ROUTES project on the requirements of the European Horizon 2020 legislation has been significant.

Establishing Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) [1]. *Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013.*

This Regulation establishes the Horizon 2020 Framework Program for Research and Innovation for the period 2014-2020 ('Horizon 2020 Programme').

Main objectives. This Regulation establishes the framework on the basis of which the European Union supports research and innovation activities. This will strengthen Europe's scientific and technological base and increase the benefits to society. It also enables better exploitation of economic and industrial potential through innovation, research and technological development. The general objective of the Horizon 2020 program is to contribute to the construction of a society and economy based on knowledge and innovation throughout the European Union. Therefore, Horizon 2020 is a measure for supporting European research and development activities, increasing technical capacity for the benefit of the economy and society. These general objectives have also been kept in mind when implementing and conducting the 5G-ROUTES project.

Legal and ethical foundations and principles. Legal and ethical foundations and principles related to scientific research are reflected at a higher level in this Horizon 2020 regulation. In the case of measures falling within the scope of this regulation, it is important to respect fundamental rights and to follow the principles recognized in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights. Such measures should be consistent with all legally binding obligations. This includes international law, relevant Commission decisions, ethical and research integrity principles. It is important to emphasize that the research and innovation activities supported by the Horizon 2020 program must follow the basic principles of ethics. Horizon 2020 should have due consideration for equal treatment and non-discrimination in research and innovation content throughout all stages of the research cycle. The higher level legal and ethical requirements of the 5G-ROUTES project originate from this regulation. It also refers to the need for taking into account the principles of equal treatment and non-discrimination in research, development and innovation activities. Since 5G-ROUTES is an international project, adherence to the principle of equal treatment and non-discrimination has been important.

Gender dimension and equality. The Horizon 2020 program aims to ensure the effective promotion of gender equality and the gender dimension in research and innovation activities. Special attention is paid to ensuring gender balance. It is desired to take this into account in the relevant research and innovation field, evaluation committee and advisory and expert groups. The gender dimension is integrated in strategies, programs and projects of research and innovation activities and is monitored at all stages of the research cycle. Due to the aforementioned principles, the issue of gender balance has also been followed in the 5G-ROUTES project. The gender balance of the 5G-ROUTES project is specifically addressed in the section on gender perspective in this document.

Legislation related to establishment and implementation of the European Horizon 2020 participation and dissemination.

Laying down the rules for participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)". Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 [2].

Main objectives. This Regulation establishes rules for participation and dissemination in the Framework Program for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 for the period 2014-2020. This regulation has been important for carrying out the activities of the 5G-ROUTES project. It is worth emphasizing that the next framework program supporting European science and innovation, Horizon Europe, followed Horizon 2020. In the following, the focus is on what the Horizon 2020 framework provides for the implementation of the field of ethics.

Commission Ethics Review. According to the *Article 14 Ethics review* – the Commission shall systematically carry out ethics reviews for proposals raising ethical issues. That review shall verify the respect of ethical principles and legislation. The Commission shall make the process of the ethics review as transparent as possible and ensure that it is carried out in a timely manner. The ethics review was also relevant in certain preparatory stages of the

5G-ROUTES project, if necessary. This has included carrying out the necessary ethical self-assessments in the 5G-ROUTES project.

Ethical principles in Grant agreement. According to the *Article 18 Grant agreement* – the grant agreement shall, where appropriate, contain provisions ensuring the respect of ethical principles. In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, the principles of ethics are described to some extent in the grant agreement. In the course of the project, these principles and procedures have been supplemented and specified.

Implementation of ethics activities. According to the *Article 23 Implementation of actions* – participants shall comply with national legislation, regulations and ethical rules in the countries where the action will be carried out. Where appropriate, participants shall seek the approval of the relevant national or local ethics committees prior to the start of the action. In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, it has been confirmed that the participants comply with the national laws, regulations and ethical rules of the countries where the action is carried out. Also, if necessary, the project parties are ready to request the approval of the relevant national or local ethics committees before starting the activity. In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, there has also been contact with the Academic Ethics Committee of Tallinn University of Technology.

2.1.2 Fundamental human rights legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Legislation related to fundamental human rights. When implementing research, development and innovation activities of the European Union, it is important to take into account fundamental human rights legislation. The principles of fundamental human rights have been taken into account at a general level in the case of the European Horizon 2020 framework program. In the following, specific European legislation is examined in more detail. Special attention is paid to the possible impact of the legislation on aspects of research and development, including data processing, protection and privacy.

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [3]. The document setting out the foundations of European human rights is the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

Main objectives and principles. The European Union is built on fundamental rights, democracy and the rule of law. Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union provides that “The Union is founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. These values are common to the Member States in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men prevail”. The aforementioned principles also provide the basis for the starting points necessary for conducting scientific research.

The Charter enshrines the fundamental rights people enjoy in the European Union. It is a modern and comprehensive instrument protecting and promoting people’s rights and freedoms in the light of changes in society, social progress and scientific and technological developments.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights applies in conjunction with national and international fundamental rights protection systems, including the European Convention on Human Rights [4].

Rights and freedoms. The Charter of Fundamental Rights contains rights and freedoms under six titles:

- dignity;
- freedoms;
- equality;
- solidarity;
- citizens' rights;

- justice.

The aforementioned rights and freedoms also affect the conduct of research and development activities.

Implementation. The Charter of Fundamental Rights has become legally binding on the European Union with the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon, in December 2009. Therefore, the parties implementing the 5G-ROUTES project have a legally binding obligation to follow these rights and freedoms.

Modern fundamental rights. To reflect modern society, the Charter of Fundamental Rights includes 'third generation' fundamental rights, such as:

- data protection;
- guarantees on bioethics;
- transparent administration [4].

Data protection and transparent administration/ management are important principles to be followed for the 5G-ROUTES project. Personal data needs to be protected in research activities. The use of European Union funds must be transparent from the point of view of the management of research projects.

Rights affecting research. Below are some points of the Charter of Fundamental Rights that also affect research activities:

According to the *Article 3 Right to the integrity of the person* – everyone has the right to respect for his or her physical and mental integrity. The aforementioned rights also affect the conduct of research and development activities. In particular, it concerns activities in the field of biology and medicine.

According to the *Article 7 Respect for private and family life* – everyone has the right to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications. The aforementioned right affects privacy in research activities.

According to the *Article 8 Protection of personal data* – everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes. The processing of personal data must have the consent of the person or another legitimate basis provided by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority. The aforementioned points create the basis for the principles of personal data processing and protection in research activities.

According to the *Article 13 Freedom of the arts and sciences* – the arts and scientific research shall be free of constraint. Academic freedom shall be respected. The aforementioned point provides a certain academic freedom in conducting scientific research. At the same time, it must be taken into account that scientific research also has limitations arising from certain legislation and standards.

According to the *Article 21 Non-discrimination* – any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited. In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, the requirement of non-discrimination is taken into account as an important principle.

According to the *Article 23 Equality between women and men* – equality between women and men must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work and pay. The principle of equality shall not prevent the maintenance or adoption of measures providing for specific advantages in favour of the under-represented sex. Achieving gender equality has been set as a goal for the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and development projects. The principle of achieving gender equality is also the basis for the activities of the 5G-ROUTES project [5].

2.1.3 Artificial intelligence legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Legislation related to artificial intelligence (AI). Today's research and development activities and technological solutions are increasingly related to the field of artificial intelligence. Therefore, it is important to consider how developments in the field of artificial intelligence can affect the activities and results of the 5G-ROUTES project. At the same time, it is important to think about the possible potential risks that the development of the field of artificial intelligence has inevitably brought. During the implementation of the 5G-ROUTES project, there have been developments in the field of European artificial intelligence regulation, which are reviewed below.

A plan for the regulation of the field of artificial intelligence. The European Union has plan to regulate artificial intelligence. The EU wants to establish strong standards for the use of artificial intelligence. This would be the first law regulating artificial intelligence worldwide.

Main objectives. As part of the digital revolution strategy, the European Union wants to establish common standards for the use of artificial intelligence, so that it is in line with EU values. Artificial intelligence offers many opportunities to advance various fields, such as healthcare, transportation and energy. From the point of view of the 5G-ROUTES project, topics in the field of cross-border movement and transport are important.

In April 2021, the Commission proposed to harmonize the legal rules for artificial intelligence used in the European Union. The purpose of the proposal is to promote innovation, establish ethical standards and increase people's trust in artificial intelligence [6].

Promoting innovation, establishing ethical standards and increasing people's trust are among the ethical principles followed by the 5G-ROUTES project. The same principles must also be followed when incorporating artificial intelligence into research and technology.

On the one hand, it is natural that artificial intelligence promotes technical development. On the other hand, ethical requirements must be ensured when using artificial intelligence. At the same time, possible threats and risks in the use of artificial intelligence must also be evaluated and analysed. Therefore, an appropriate balance must be achieved when analysing the benefits and possible associated risks from the use of artificial intelligence.

The European Parliament demands that artificial breeding systems used in the European Union are safe, transparent, traceable, environmentally friendly and do not discriminate against anyone. The new rules must ensure that technology remains under human control. In Europe, as a democratic society, attention has been paid to ensuring human rights in the use of new technologies, including artificial intelligence. It is important to consider the aforementioned principles in the case of the technological solutions of the 5G-ROUTES project.

The need for rules on artificial intelligence. AI legislation aims to ensure that Europeans can trust what AI has to offer. While most AI systems do not pose a threat and can help solve many societal problems, certain AI systems pose a threat that must be addressed to avoid undesired outcomes.

In order to avoid unwanted consequences, threats and risks, regulations are necessary to:

- identify a list of high-risk applications;
- specifically address risks arising from applications of artificial intelligence;
- set clear requirements for AI systems for high-risk applications;
- set specific obligations for deployers and providers of high-risk AI applications;
- prohibit AI practices that pose unacceptable risks;
- require a conformity assessment before a specific artificial intelligence system is introduced or placed on the market;
- enforce post-market enforcement of a particular AI system;
- create a management structure at the European and national level [7].

Approval of the Artificial Intelligence Act. In May 2024, the Council of Europe approved legislation regulating artificial intelligence. Its purpose is to harmonize the legal regulations concerning artificial intelligence. This legislation follows a risk-based approach. This means that the greater the risk of harm to society, the stricter the norms. This is the first piece of legislation of its kind in the world and could therefore set a global standard for AI regulation.

Need for the Artificial Intelligence Act. The aim of the new regulation is to promote the development and deployment of safe and reliable artificial intelligence systems across the EU single market in both the public and private sectors. At the same time, it aims to ensure that EU citizens' fundamental rights are respected and to encourage AI-related investment and innovation in Europe [8].

Importance of the Artificial Intelligence Act. The AI Act is the first legal framework related to artificial intelligence in the world. This law addresses the risks associated with artificial intelligence and places Europe in a global leadership role.

Main objectives of the Artificial Intelligence Act. The purpose of the Artificial Intelligence Act is to provide developers and implementers of artificial intelligence with clear requirements and obligations regarding specific uses of artificial intelligence. At the same time, the regulation tries to reduce the administrative and financial burden on entrepreneurs, especially small and medium-sized enterprises. The new rules aim to promote trusted artificial intelligence in Europe and beyond.

AI policy package. The AI Act is part of a wider policy package to support the development of trusted AI. It also includes the AI Innovation Package and the AI Coordinated Plan. Together, these measures ensure the safety and fundamental rights of people and businesses in relation to artificial intelligence. They will also strengthen AI deployment, investment and innovation across the EU.

Objectives of the AI policy package. The aim is to ensure that AI systems respect fundamental rights, safety and ethical principles. There is also a need to pay attention to the risks of powerful and influential artificial intelligence models [9].

It is important to assess the impacts and risks of the AI Act and the AI policy package in the future in the perspective of the further use of the technological results of the 5G-ROUTES project.

Classification of artificial intelligence systems. In the new regulation, different types of artificial intelligence systems are classified according to risk. Limited risk AI systems are subject to very lenient transparency obligations. High-risk AI systems may be authorized but subject to certain requirements and obligations to enter the EU market. Artificial intelligence systems such as cognitive behavior manipulation and social scoring are banned in the EU because the risk involved is considered unacceptable. The regulation bans systems that use biometric data to classify people according to specific categories such as race, religion or social orientation.

Risk levels. The new regulation establishes obligations for service providers and users depending on the risk level of the artificial intelligence system. The possible further use of the technologies of the 5G-ROUTES project in connection with artificial intelligence may require an assessment of the level of risks that may arise.

A risk-based approach. The four risk levels defined in the legislative framework for artificial intelligence systems are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The four risk levels defined in the legislative framework for artificial intelligence systems [9].

High risk artificial intelligence systems. Systems that significantly affect the security and fundamental rights of users are classified as high-risk AI systems. They are divided into two categories.

- Artificial intelligence systems covered by the EU General Product Safety Directive. For example: toys, cars, medical devices and elevators.
- Artificial intelligence systems in eight areas to be registered in the EU database.

High-risk AI systems include AI technology used to:

- vital infrastructures that may threaten the life and health of citizens (e.g. transport);
- educational or vocational training that may determine a person's access to an education and vocational course (e.g. exams assessment);
- product safety features (e.g. use of artificial intelligence in robotic surgery);
- employment, staff management and access to self-employment (e.g. CV sorting software for recruitment processes);
- important private and public services (e.g. provision of credit points that prevent citizens from obtaining loans);
- legal protection that may affect people's fundamental rights (e.g. assessing the reliability of evidence);
- management of migration, asylum and border control (e.g. automatic review of visa applications);
- administration of justice and democratic processes (e.g. artificial intelligence solutions for searching judgments).

High-risk AI systems are subject to strict obligations before being placed on the market:

- adequate risk assessment and mitigation systems;
- high quality of the data sets underlying the system to minimize risks and discriminatory results;
- activity logging to ensure traceability of results;

- detailed documentation that provides all the information about the system and its purpose that the authorities need to assess the system's compliance with the requirements;
- clear and sufficient information for the implementer;
- appropriate human supervision measures to minimize risk;
- high level of reliability, security and accuracy.

All remote biometric recognition systems are considered high-risk systems and are subject to strict requirements. The use of biometric remote identification in publicly accessible premises for law enforcement purposes is prohibited in principle.

Limited risk. Limited risk refers to the risks associated with the lack of transparency in the use of artificial intelligence. AI legislation sets out specific transparency obligations to ensure that people are informed when necessary and to build trust.

The risk is minimal or non-existent. The legislation on artificial intelligence allows the free use of artificial intelligence with minimal risk. This includes applications such as artificial intelligence-based video games or spam filters. Most AI systems currently in use in the European Union fall into this category.

Prohibited artificial intelligence systems. From the point of view of research and development, it is important to keep in mind that the use of certain artificial intelligence systems is prohibited. Artificial branch systems that are dangerous to people are prohibited. It includes:

- systems that can exploit the weaknesses of specific vulnerable groups to significantly influence their behavior (for example, voice-activated toys);
- systems that allow people to be scored based on social indicators;
- biometric personal identification systems (for example, facial recognition).

General Purpose Artificial Intelligence Models. The AI Regulation also addresses the use of general purpose AI models. General-purpose AI models that do not involve systemic risks have few requirements, such as transparency, but models with systemic risks must meet more stringent requirements.

Transparency and protection of fundamental rights. Before public entities adopt a high-risk AI system, their impact on fundamental rights must be assessed. The regulation also provides for greater transparency regarding the use of high-risk AI systems. High-risk AI systems and certain high-risk AI system users who are public sector bodies must be registered in the EU's high-risk AI systems database. Users of emotion recognition systems must notify natural persons when they encounter such a system.

Penalties and sanctions. Fines for breaches of the AI Regulation are set either as a percentage of the offending company's total global turnover for the previous financial year or as a fixed amount, whichever is greater. Proportionate administrative fines apply to SMEs and start-ups.

Measures supporting innovation. The AI Regulation creates an innovation-friendly legal framework and aims to promote evidence-based regulatory learning. The new regulation stipulates that TIs regulatory sandboxes, which should create a controlled environment for the development, testing and validation of innovative AI systems, should enable the testing of novel AI systems under real-world conditions [9].

The possible further use of the technologies of the 5G-ROUTES project in connection with artificial intelligence may require an assessment of the level of risks that may arise.

In the technological solutions of the 5G-ROUTES project, there is an implicit opportunity to use high-risk artificial intelligence systems in relation to vital infrastructure, public services and border control.

2.1.4 Cyber security legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Legislation related to cyber security. Research and development activities and technological solutions are influenced by developments in the field of cyber security. Developments in the field of cyber security are also important in terms of the implementation and technological results of the 5G-ROUTES project. In the following, the most important developments in the field of cyber security and their possible effects are examined.

NIS Directive: Directive on measures aimed at ensuring a uniformly high level of security of network and information systems throughout the Union. In July 2016, the European Parliament and the Council adopted Directive (EU) No. 2016/1148 on measures aimed at ensuring a uniformly high level of security of network and information systems throughout the Union.

Main objectives. The member states had the obligation to adopt and publish the legal regulations necessary for the implementation of the directive by May 2018. The NIS directive stipulates that national law establishes requirements for the implementation and notification of security measures for essential service and digital service providers. Therefore, the countries of the parties participating in the 5G-ROUTES project must implement the requirements arising from this directive, which also have a certain impact on the project parties.

The purpose of the NIS directive is to ensure a high level of security of network and information systems throughout the European Union. The NIS directive instructs the member states to implement the corresponding measures, based on the specific characteristics of the country and the current legal system.

Main principles. Article 1 of the directive sets out the scope of regulation and application. The purpose of the directive is to establish measures to achieve a uniformly high level of security of network and information systems in the Union, thereby improving the functioning of the internal market.

According to Article 3 of the directive, Member States may adopt or maintain provisions with the aim of achieving a higher level of network and information system security.

Article 6 of the directive talks about a significant disruptive effect on the provision of essential services and stipulates cross-sectoral factors that member states must take into account.

Article 7 of the directive stipulates the national security strategy for network and information systems. Each Member State is obliged to adopt a strategy for the security of network and information systems, which defines strategic objectives and appropriate policy and regulatory measures to achieve and maintain a high level of security of network and information systems.

Articles 14 and 15 of the directive focus on the security of network and information systems of operators of essential services. Member States must ensure that operators of essential services take appropriate and proportionate technical and organizational measures to manage risks that threaten the security of the network and information systems used in their work.

Articles 16-18 of the directive focus on the security of digital service providers' network and information systems and incident reporting. Member States must ensure that digital service providers identify risks related to the security of the network and information systems they use to provide the services referred to in the Directive in the Union and take appropriate and proportionate technical and organizational measures to mitigate these risks. This has an indirect impact on the possible use of 5G-ROUTES technologies.

Articles 19 of the directive focus on standardization. Member States shall encourage the use of European or internationally approved standards and specifications to ensure the security of network and information systems, without requiring or encouraging the use of certain types of technology [10]. The principle of proportionality in research ethics is related to the principle of equal treatment of technologies, which has also had to be kept in mind for the technologies of the 5G-ROUTES project.

The measures provided by the directive to increase the level of general security have been useful in the implementation of the 5G-ROUTES project and in ensuring the security of the further use of its technological solutions.

NIS2 Directive: Directive on measures to ensure a uniformly high level of cybersecurity across the Union – Cybersecurity Directive 2 [11]. The EU cybersecurity rules introduced in 2016 were updated with the second cybersecurity directive, NIS2 – Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union. NIS2 entered into force in 2023. It updated the existing legal framework to keep pace with digitization and the changing cyber security threat landscape. The aim of the subsequent cyber security directive was to further harmonize the level of cyber security in the member states.

Main objectives. This Directive sets out measures aimed at achieving a uniformly high level of cyber security across the Union in order to improve the functioning of the internal market. NIS2 sets out legal measures to increase the overall level of cybersecurity in the EU by ensuring:

- Member States' preparedness by requiring them to be properly equipped.
- cooperation between all Member States by establishing a Cooperation Group to support and facilitate strategic cooperation and exchange of information between Member States.
- a culture of security in all sectors that are vital to our economy and society and highly dependent on ICT, such as energy, transport, water, banking, financial market infrastructures, health and digital infrastructure.

Businesses identified by Member States as operators of essential services in the aforementioned sectors must take appropriate security measures and notify relevant public authorities of serious incidents. Essential services also extend to technological solutions that are related to the results of the 5G-ROUTES project [12].

Main principles. According to the *Article 1 Subject matter* – This Directive lays down measures aimed at achieving a uniformly high level of cyber security throughout the Union in order to improve the functioning of the internal market. In order to achieve this goal, this directive stipulates:

- the obligation of Member States to adopt national cyber security strategies and to designate or establish competent authorities, cyber crisis management bodies, cyber security single contact points and cyber security incident response units;
- cyber security risk management measures and notification obligation of entities considered vital in accordance with Directive (EU) 2022/2557;
- rules and obligations related to the exchange of information on cyber security;
- obligations to Member States related to supervision and enforcement.

This Directive shall also apply to:

- providers of publicly available electronic communications networks or providers of publicly available electronic communications services;
- entities which, due to their special importance, are of critical importance at the national or regional level for a certain sector or type of service or other interdependent sectors in a Member State.

According to the *Article 7 National cyber security strategy* – Each Member State shall adopt a national cyber security strategy, which shall define strategic objectives, the resources necessary to achieve these objectives and appropriate political and regulatory measures to achieve and maintain a high level of cyber security. Taking into account the national cyber security strategy in the view of projects developing 5G technologies is expedient to keep in mind. The implementation of the national cyber strategy will definitely have a security impact on the use of the results of the 5G-ROUTES project.

According to the *Article 8 Competent authorities and single points of contact* – Each Member State shall designate or establish at least one competent authority responsible for cyber security and the performance of the supervisory tasks. Each Member State shall designate or establish one contact point. Each single point of contact performs a liaison function to ensure cross-border cooperation between the authorities of its Member State with the relevant authorities of other Member States and, where appropriate, with the Commission and ENISA, as well as cross-sectoral cooperation with other competent authorities of its Member State. The aforementioned points are important for the 5G-ROUTES project in terms of communication on cross-border cyber security issues.

According to the *Article 24 Use of European cybersecurity certification schemes* – Member States may require vital and important entities to use certain ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes developed by the vital or important entity or procured from third parties to demonstrate compliance with certain requirements and which is certified on the basis of the European cybersecurity certification schemes.

According to the *Article 25 Standardization* – Member States shall support the implementation of European and international standards and technical specifications concerning the security of network and information systems, without requiring or discriminatingly favoring the use of a specific type of technology. The equal treatment of technologies needs to be observed from the point of view of the proportionality principle of scientific ethics [11].

The aforementioned certification and standardization articles should also be kept in mind for the technologies of the 5G-ROUTES project.

2.1.5 Electronic communications legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Legislation related to electronic communications. From the point of view of research and development activities and the use of technology, it is also important to comply with electronic communications legislation. In order to harmonize the field of telecommunications, a corresponding directive has been developed in Europe.

Electronic Communications Code. Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code.

Main objectives. This Directive establishes a harmonized framework regulating electronic communications networks, electronic communications services and related equipment and services, as well as certain aspects related to terminal equipment. This Directive lays down the obligations of national regulatory authorities and, where applicable, other competent authorities, and establishes arrangements to ensure uniform application of the regulatory framework across the Union. The objectives of this Directive are:

- to implement an internal market for electronic communications networks and services, which achieves the deployment and commissioning of very high capacity networks, sustainable competition, interoperability of electronic communications services, accessibility, security of networks and services and benefits for end users;
- to ensure the provision of public services of good quality and affordable prices throughout the Union through effective competition and freedom of choice, address situations where the market does not effectively meet the needs of end-users, including users with disabilities, so that they can access services on an equal basis with others, and establish the necessary rights of end-users.

Main principles. National regulatory authorities and other competent authorities shall take all reasonable measures that are necessary and proportionate to achieve the objectives set out in this Directive.

National regulatory authorities and other competent authorities shall comply with all of the following general objectives:

- promote the connection, access and commissioning of all Union citizens and businesses to very high capacity networks, including fixed, mobile and wireless networks;

- support competition in the provision of electronic communication networks and related means, including effective infrastructure-based competition, and in the provision of electronic communication services and related services;
- contribute to the development of the internal market by removing remaining barriers across the Union affecting investment in electronic communications networks, electronic communications services, related equipment and services on the one hand. On the other hand, to promote the creation of equal opportunities in the provision of these networks, devices and services;
- develop common standards and a predictable regulatory approach, foster effective, efficient and coordinated use of radio spectrum, open innovation, creation and development of pan-European networks, pan-European service provision, availability and interoperability and connectivity;
- promote the interests of citizens of the Union by ensuring connectivity to very high-capacity networks, including fixed, mobile and wireless networks and electronic communications services, and their widespread availability and uptake, enabling maximum benefit in terms of choice, price and quality based on effective competition,
- maintain the security of networks and services, ensure a high and consistent level of end-user protection through the necessary sector-specific standards, and
- pay attention to the needs of specific social groups, in particular disabled end-users, elderly end-users and end-users with special social needs, such as affordable prices, and choice and equal access for disabled end-users [13].

In the view of the 5G-ROUTES project, it was necessary to pay general attention to the aforementioned directive in the part that concerns the harmonized framework and regulation of electronic communication networks, electronic communication services and related equipment and services.

2.2 Finnish research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Since parts of the implementation of research, development and innovation activities of the 5G-ROUTES project has been related to Finland, Finnish regulations are reviewed below.

1. The main regulation of research, development and innovation activities. In Finland, research, development and innovation activities are regulated by the Government Decree on the Research and Innovation Council of Finland. The Research and Innovation Council of Finland is responsible for solving important issues related to the direction, follow-up, evaluation and coordination of science, technology and innovation policy. The Council assists the Government and its ministries in matters within the competence of the Council.

The Research and Innovation Council is an advisory body of the state administration, consisting of members of the Government and external expert members.

The government appointed new members to the Research and Innovation Council in November 2023. The goal of the Research and Innovation Council is to support the government in the formulation of a long-term comprehensive research and innovation policy [14].

Main purpose. The purpose of the Research and Innovation Council is to:

- support the Government in developing its long-term comprehensive research and innovation policy;
- present initiatives for national strategy choices;
- monitor changes in the operating environment;

- promote Finland's image as a country with a favourable research and innovation policy;
- coordinate and monitor the implementation of the Act on Research and Development Funding and the drafting and implementation of the multiannual plan for the use of research and development funding;
- prepare initiatives related to research and innovation policy;
- present proposals for the allocation of Research and Developing funding [15].

2. Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. In Finland, the development and innovation of electronic communications is regulated by Act on Electronic Communications Services [16].

Main purpose. The purpose of the Act on Electronic Communications Services is to foster the provision and use of electronic communications services and to ensure that everyone across Finland has access to communications networks and services at reasonable conditions. A further objective of the Act is to secure the efficient and interference-free use of radio frequencies, to foster competition, and to ensure that communications networks and services are technologically advanced, of high quality, reliable, safe, and inexpensive. This Act also aims to ensure the confidentiality of electronic communication and the protection of privacy.

Main content. The Act contains provisions on the rights, obligations and responsibilities of several entities and their customers in the context of electronic services and communications.

3. Cyber Security legislation. Finland does not have a general cyber security law or framework. More detailed security requirements are in sectoral laws.

2.3 Estonian research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Since parts of the implementation of research, development and innovation activities of the 5G-ROUTES project has been related to Estonia, Estonian regulations are reviewed below.

1. The main regulation of research, development and innovation activities. In Estonia, research, development and innovation activities are regulated by the Organisation of Research and Development Act [17].

Main purpose. The purpose of the Organization of Research and Development Act is to establish the foundations of the organization of research and development activities, to ensure the legal means for the preservation and further development of scientific and technological creation as a component of Estonian culture and economy.

Problems with current legislation. The current Organization of Research and Development Act was adopted in 1997. Over the course of more than twenty years, expectations for the organization of research and development activities have changed, the circle of research and development institutions and expectations for their activities have changed. The Organization of Research and Development Act has been amended more than 20 times. As a result of many changes, the focus of the law has become scattered, and the law as a whole needs to be put in order.

The need to update the legislation. The purpose of amending the act is to organize the act as a whole and bring it into line with the changed expectations for research and development activities, as well as to more clearly stipulate the parties of the research and development system, their roles and responsibilities. One of the major topics is the specification of financing principles with the aim of enabling more performance management and direction than before. Activities to develop the new act began in the summer of 2020, with the goal of enforcing the act in 2023 [18].

The process and procedure for updating legislation. The draft of the Organization of Research and Development and Innovation Act, together with an explanatory letter, was submitted for approval at the end of 2022. The bill establishes the Organization of Research and Development Act as a new complete text to regulate the field of research and development and innovation. The existing Organization of Research and Development Act is declared invalid. According to the draft, the Organization of Research and Development Act lays down the bases for the national organization of research and development activities, the evaluation of the activities and quality of research and development institutions, and the funding of research and development activities and innovation. The need for new legislation in the field of research, development and innovation is also related to additional ethical principles and procedures [19]. Parliament is still adopting the law.

2. Cyber Security legislation. In Estonia, the field of cyber security is regulated by the Cyber Security Act [20].

Goal. This Cyber Security Act stipulates the requirements for the maintenance of network and information systems of the public sector, responsibility and supervision, as well as the bases for the prevention and resolution of cyber incidents, which are important from the point of view of the functioning of society.

Requirements for national cyber security legislation. In July 2016, the European Parliament and the Council adopted Directive on measures to ensure a uniformly high level of security of network and information systems throughout the Union (NIS Directive). The member states had the obligation to adopt and publish the legal regulations necessary for the implementation of the directive by May 2018. The NIS directive stipulates that national law establishes requirements for the implementation of security measures and notification for providers of essential services and digital services.

Purpose of the act. The purpose of the Cyber Security Act is:

- to adopt the NIS directive into the Estonian legal space; and
- to establish national measures to ensure the security of network and information systems that are vital and important from the point of view of maintaining social and economic activity.

The act establishes the principles of ensuring cyber security, the rights and obligations of individuals in ensuring cyber security in network and information systems, and the supervision of the fulfilment of these requirements. With the implementation of the NIS directive, cyber security cooperation between member states will be strengthened and harmonized.

Main objectives. The objectives of the Act are:

- to establish clear and uniform rights and obligations to ensure cyber security in the provision of services that are vital and important from the point of view of maintaining social and economic activity and that depend on network and information systems; as well as ensure uniform security and notification requirements for digital service providers operating in the EU internal market in accordance with the requirements set forth in the NIS Directive.
- to improve the reporting of important cyber incidents and threats in order to improve the ability to prevent, detect and respond to cyber incidents that affect the functioning of society and the economy. The notification mechanism makes it possible to improve the preparedness of the state as well as the public and the private sector to deal with cyber incidents and increase the involvement of the latter. At the same time, the protection of sensitive business information and personal data is ensured.
- to improve the European Union's threat awareness and responsiveness to cross-border cyber incidents through the provision of notification obligations and incident-related information exchange arrangements.

- to establish the basis for the prevention, identification and suppression of cyber threats by establishing the competence of the State Information System Board in the exercise of national and administrative supervision.

Main principles. Cyber Security Act, § 1 provides the scope of the law. Section 1 sets out the area of influence of the law, which is the requirements for maintaining network and information systems that are important from the point of view of the functioning of the state and society, the basics of preventing and solving cyber incidents, and monitoring the fulfilment of the obligations stipulated in the law.

Considering the fact that in today's world, most of the provided services are more or less dependent on network and information systems, it is necessary to ensure the security and reliability of the systems. In order to prevent possible manipulations or even intentional attacks and to reduce the damage caused by them, it is necessary to create a uniform and clear regulation that stipulates the obligations of various parties, with the aim of protecting public order, the health and property of individuals, and the general order of life in society.

Cyber Security Act, § 3 stipulates the scope of application of the law. The section lists the service providers to whom the law in question applies. Clause 1, point 1 stipulates that the law applies to the vital service provider provided for in § 36 of the Emergency Act regarding the information systems and related information assets used for the provision of the vital service. In the Emergency Act, the list of vital services includes electricity supply, natural gas supply, liquid fuel supply, ensuring the drivability of the national road, **telephone service, mobile phone service, data communication service**, electronic identification and digital signature, emergency assistance operation, payment service, cash circulation, district heating supply, ensuring the drivability of the local road and water supply, and channel zone.

Cyber Security Act, § 6 sets out the principles at the level of the law, which are guided by the goal of the NIS directive to promote the culture of risk management, thereby also fulfilling the task of raising awareness.

The principle of personal diligence defined in Section 6, Clause 1 stipulates that the primary responsibility for ensuring the security of one's network and information system rests with its administrator. Since 2008, the organization of Estonian cyber security as a whole has been based on the assumption that every participant in the information society is responsible for the security of a technical device or system with a network connection in his possession. The prerequisite for good information security is that the owner of the information system is aware of his responsibility and implements security measures corresponding to the identified risks. According to the aforementioned OECD recommendation, every information system owner is also expected to be aware of the risks of the digital environment affecting their operations and to take responsibility for their management.

Point 2 sets out the principle of comprehensive protection. If the principle of personal diligence explains the location of responsibility, this principle opens up the content of the duty of care: ensuring acceptable security requires the identification of specific risks threatening the system and the implementation of appropriate organizational and technical measures to protect the system. In a specific case, risk management can consist of risk acceptance, reduction, transfer and avoidance, but must be appropriate, taking into account the possible impact of the realization of risks on the owner of the information system as well as on the legitimate interests of other persons.

The principle of reducing the harmful impact stipulated in point 3 stipulates that measures must be taken in the event of a cyber incident to limit the negative impact of the incident on other systems as well as on the legal benefits of other persons, and means that it must also have the desired effect in society - prevention of the threat and its rapid suppression.

The means of minimizing the impact of a cyber incident are the necessary technological and organizational measures as well as notification of the cyber incident [10].

3. Electronic Communications Legislation. In Estonia, the development and innovation of electronic communications is regulated by the Electronic Communications Act [21].

The purpose of the Act. Purpose of this Act is:

- to create the necessary conditions for the development of electronic communications;
- to promote the development of electronic communications networks and services without favoring specific technologies; and
- to ensure the protection of the interests of electronic communications service users by promoting free competition and the expedient and fair planning, allocation and use of radio frequencies and numbering.

Main principles. This act stipulates the requirements for publicly available electronic communication networks and services, the use of electronic contact data for direct marketing, maintaining radio communications, managing radio frequencies and numbering, and radio equipment, as well as state supervision of the fulfilment of these requirements and responsibility for the violation of these requirements.

2.4 Latvian research, development and innovation legislation, regulations, rules and procedures

Since parts of the implementation of research, development and innovation activities of the 5G-ROUTES project has been related to Latvia, Latvian regulations are reviewed below.

1. The main regulation of research, development and innovation activities. In Latvia, research, development and innovation activities are regulated by Law on Scientific Activity [22]. The purpose of this Law is to strengthen the role of the State in the fostering of science as a particularly important factor in the development of society.

Main purpose. This law stipulates the unity of science and higher education, the rights and obligations of researchers, independence and academic freedom, professional and social insurance, and the competence and obligations of the state authorities in ensuring research activities.

The right to scientific activity. According to Section 3 of the Law, every person, regardless of race, ethnicity, gender, language, age, political or religious beliefs, social origin or material, family or professional situation and other circumstances, has the right to scientific activity. The right to scientific activity is based on the fundamental rights of people, including equality and non-discrimination. Equality and non-discrimination of people have been observed in the implementation of the 5G-ROUTES project.

Research transparency. Information about research funded from the state or local government budget must be transparent. General access to research results is ensured by the institution responsible for conducting scientific research financed from the state budget or from the budget of derived public entities, which has ordered the research. Access to research-related information may be restricted in cases provided by law. When funding research projects, it is necessary that the use of resources is transparent and understandable. The results of research must be available to the wider society. The principle of research transparency has been taken into account in the implementation of 5G-ROUTES management and research activities.

2. Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. In Latvia, the field of electronic communications development is regulated by the Electronic Communications Law [23].

Purpose of the Law. The purpose of this Law is:

- promote the development of the market of electronic communication services;
- promote the development of competition in the provision of electronic communication networks, including effective infrastructure-based competition, and in the provision of electronic communication services;

- promote the provision of electronic communication networks, especially very high performance networks, and the development of electronic communication services;
- ensure regulation of electronic communication networks and electronic communication services that are neutral from electronic communication technology;
- ensure rational and efficient use of numbering, radio frequency spectrum and the top-level domain ".lv";
- ensure the use of a harmonized radio frequency spectrum;
- ensure the protection of the interests of the state, end users and electronic communications merchants;
- promote the availability of the universal service;
- ensure the integrity and compatibility of electronic communication networks, continuity of provision of electronic communication services;
- ensure the protection of end-user data, including personal data, when providing electronic communication services.

Scope of the Law. The Law determines the competence, rights and obligations of end-users, electronic communications merchants, owners of private electronic communications networks and state administrative institutions related to the regulation of the electronic communications industry, the provision of electronic communications networks, the provision of electronic communications services, as well as the use of numbering and radio frequency spectrum use and management and management of the top-level domain ".lv".

The Law also applies to the electronic communication networks necessary for the distribution of radio or television programs.

The Law does not apply to the provision of information society services and content services and to the content of information transmitted or received in electronic communication networks.

3. Cyber Security legislation. In Latvia, the field of cyber security is regulated by the National Cyber Security Law. In June 2024, the Latvian Parliament adopted the National Cyber Security Law [24].

Purpose of the Law. The purpose of this Law is to strengthen cyber security in Latvia and to implement the requirements of the revised Directive on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2 Directive), which aims to achieve a uniformly high level of cyber security across the European Union.

Implementation of the Law. The law applies to providers of essential and important services, as well as critical infrastructure of information and communication technology. Article 20 and 21 of the law sets out criteria for defining whether a public or private sector organisation belongs to one of these groups.

Providers of essential and important services in the public and private sectors will also be required to provide regular cyber security self-assessments, mandatory reporting of detected cyber threats, risk management and business continuity plans and adhere to other cybersecurity requirements.

Main objectives. The main objectives of the law are:

- improve the security of information and communication technologies, including setting requirements for the provision and receipt of essential services and important services, as well as the operation of information and communication technologies;
- determine the procedure for ensuring cyber security, foreseeing the distribution of responsibility and the competence of the National Cyber Security Center, cooperation frameworks and cyber security promotion tasks;

- promote the implementation of cyber security measures in such a way as to be able to predict and prevent them in time, as well as to overcome cyber threats and eliminate their consequences, ensuring the continuity of confidentiality, integrity and availability of services as much as possible.

Application of the law. The law applies to the following entities:

- providers of essential services, providers of important services and owners and legal holders of critical infrastructure of information and communication technologies;
- direct and intermediate administrative institutions, derived public entities and other state institutions, as well as legal entities of private law that perform a task delegated by the state administration, with the exception of state security institutions;
- private law legal entities;
- in the cases specified in this law – for natural persons participating in the coordinated vulnerability detection process [25].

Law on the Security of Information Technologies. In Latvia, the field of security of IT technologies is regulated by the Law on the Security of Information Technologies.

Purpose of the Law. The purpose of the Law on the Security of Information Technologies is to improve the security of information technologies, laying down the most important requirements in order to guarantee the receipt of such essential services, in the supply of which such technologies are used.

The security of information technologies shall be guarded in such a way that it is possible to make early forecasts and to prevent, as well as to overcome danger to such security and eliminate the consequences thereof.

Application of the Law. This Law shall apply to State and local government authorities, as well as merchants and other legal persons governed by private law. This Law shall not apply to the content of the information transmitted in electronic communications networks.

Critical infrastructure. The critical infrastructure of information technologies is an infrastructure, which is approved by the Cabinet in accordance with the National Security Law.

The critical infrastructure of information technologies shall be defended in order to provide the performance of the basic functions essential to the State and society. Moreover, the integrity, availability and confidentiality of the critical infrastructure of information technologies shall be ensured.

The procedures for the planning and implementation of security measures for the critical infrastructure of information technologies shall be stipulated by the Cabinet [26].

2.5 Data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities

2.5.1 European Union data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities

The following chapter examines data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures in relation to research, development and innovation activities.

1. The main regulation of personal data protection. The General Data Protection Regulation is a European Union privacy regulation that came into effect on May 25, 2018 [27].

Goal. The General Data Protection Regulation was created with the goal of giving individuals greater control over their personal data. This is an important effort to protect individual rights and freedoms.

Application. The General Data Protection Regulation applies to all organizations located in the European Union, as well as to organizations, regardless of their location, that sell goods and provide services in the European Union or process personal data of European Union citizens in the European Union and elsewhere.

Purpose of the legislation. According to the legislation of the European Union, the protection of natural persons in the processing of personal data is a fundamental right.

Article 8(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and Article 16(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union provide that everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.

Main objectives. The regulations and principles for the protection of natural persons in the processing of their personal data should respect their fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular the right to the protection of personal data, regardless of their nationality or place of residence.

When using personal data both in general and in research contexts, it is important to emphasize that the processing of personal data should be designed to serve mankind.

Exceptions. It is also necessary to point out that the right to personal data protection is not an absolute right; it must be considered in relation to its function in society and must be balanced against other fundamental rights in accordance with the principle of proportionality.

Balance between data processing, protection and privacy. Regarding the principles of the 5G-ROUTES project and the General Data Protection Regulation, it is important to emphasize that the economic and social integration resulting from the operation of the internal market has led to a significant increase in cross-border movements of personal data. This, in turn, means that there must be a balance between the increasingly extensive need for personal data processing resulting from economic and social integration and the need for data protection based on privacy.

Main principles. The General Data Protection Regulation stipulates compliance with the following principles:

- legality, fairness and transparency;
- limitation of purpose;
- data minimization;
- accuracy;
- storage limitation;
- integrity and confidentiality;
- liability.

In terms of data processing, protection and privacy, the 5G-ROUTES project has had to be implemented in a way that protects the fundamental rights of natural persons.

2. Data protection officer. The data protection officer is an important role in terms of personal data protection. The European General Data Protection Regulation provides for the appointment of a data protection officer in certain cases.

The data protection officer monitors the processing and protection of personal data in the organization. The data protection officer helps the organization to ensure compliance with regulations on the processing and protection

of personal data. The data protection officer, among other things, audits and monitors the processing and protection of personal data in the organization.

Designation of the data protection officer. Pursuant to Article 37 of the General Data Protection Regulation [27], the data controller and data processor appoint a data protection officer in any case if:

- the processing is carried out by a public authority – institution or body;
- the main activity of the data controller or data processor consists of processing operations that, due to their nature, scope and/ or purposes, require regular and systematic large scale/ wide-ranging monitoring of data subjects; or
- their core activities consist of processing special category personal data on a large scale.

Basis for appointing a data protection officer. The appointment of the data protection officer is based on his/ her:

- professional skills;
- expert knowledge of data protection law and practice; and
- ability to perform the duties.

Performing the duties of the data protection officer. The data protection officer may be an employee of the data controller or data processor or perform tasks on the basis of a service contract. The data protection officer may perform other duties and responsibilities. The controller or authorized processor ensures that such tasks and responsibilities do not lead to a conflict of interest.

Publication of data protection officer information. The data controller or data processor publishes the contact details of the data protection officer and reports them to the supervisory authority.

More specific instructions on data protection officers. The Article 29 Working Party has issued Guidelines on Data Protection Officers (WP243) [28].

Position of data protection officer. The data controller and data processor ensures the proper and timely involvement of the data protection officer in all matters related to the protection of personal data.

Support for the data protection officer. The data controller and the data processor shall support the data protection officer in the performance of the tasks by providing him or her with the necessary tools to perform these tasks and maintain the level of expertise, as well as access to personal data and personal data processing operations.

Ensuring the independence of the data protection officer. The data controller and the data processor ensure that the data protection officer does not receive instructions regarding the performance of these tasks. The data controller or data processor cannot dismiss or punish him or her for the performance of his duties. The data protection officer reports directly to the highest management level of the controller or processor.

Being a point of contact for data subjects. Data subjects may contact the data protection officer in all matters related to the processing of their personal data and the exercise of their rights arising from this regulation.

Confidentiality requirement. The data protection officer is subject to the requirement of secrecy or confidentiality in the performance of his/ her duties in accordance with the law of the European Union or Member State.

Exceptions and recommendations. In the event that the appointment of a data protection officer is not obvious, the Article 29 Working Party [28] recommends that data controllers and data processors document an internal analysis of the need to appoint a data protection officer. This is necessary to decide whether or not to appoint a data protection officer. In this case, the data controller and the data processor can prove, if necessary, that they have correctly taken the relevant factors into account.

Scope of activity of the data protection officer. According to the Guidelines for Data Protection Officers issued by the Article 29 Working Party (WP243) [28], the data protection officer, whether mandatory or voluntary, is designated for all the processing operations carried out by the controller or the processor.

Therefore, if the organization participating in the 5G-ROUTES project has appointed a data protection officer, his/ her activities include, among other things, dealing with personal data processing operations of this research and development project.

Other ways to coordinate data protection. An organization that is not required by law to appoint a data protection officer and does not wish to appoint a data protection officer on a voluntary basis is not prohibited from hiring employees or external consultants in connection with tasks related to the protection of personal data. In this case, it is important to make sure that there is no confusion about their title, status, status and duties [28].

Within the research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, in the absence of a data protection officer, it has been recommended to appoint persons who would be responsible for data management and protection.

Tasks of the data protection officer. Based on the General Data Protection Regulation [27], the data protection officer has at least the following tasks:

- to inform and advise the data controller or data processor and employees processing personal data in relation to their obligations arising from the General Data Protection Regulation and other data protection regulations of the Union or member states;
- monitor compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation, other data protection regulations of the Union or member states and the personal data protection principles of the data controller or data processor, including the allocation of areas of responsibility, awareness raising and training of personnel involved in personal data processing, and related auditing;
- upon request, provide advice regarding the data protection impact assessment and monitor its performance;
- to cooperate with the supervisory authority;
- to act as a contact person for the supervisory authority in matters of personal data processing, including the prior consultation;
- and to consult on other issues if necessary.

Possible additional tasks. European Union member states and organizations can assign additional tasks to data protection officers. It is important to emphasize that the data protection officer may perform other duties and responsibilities. The data controller or data processor ensures that such tasks and responsibilities do not lead to a conflict of interest.

The issue of conflict of interest. The absence of conflict of interest is closely related to the requirement that the data protection officer can act in an independent manner. Although data protection officers have the right to perform other actions, they can be assigned other tasks and duties only on the condition that they do not create conflicts of interest. First of all, this means that the data protection officer cannot be in a position in the organization, as a result of which he/ she has to decide on the purposes and means of personal data processing. Since the organizational structure is different in every organization, the situation must be considered on a case-by-case basis [28].

From the point of view of the 5G-ROUTES project, it has been important to note that the person deciding on the goals and means of research and development data processing would not be a data protection officer at the same time.

3. Data protection impact assessment. The General Data Protection Regulation adds a new general liability obligation to not only comply with the rules, but also to be able to demonstrate compliance. A data protection impact assessment must be conducted where “high risk” processing is carried out.

In accordance with the data protection impact assessment of Article 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation [27], in certain cases, prior to processing, the data processor carries out an assessment of the impact of the planned processing operations on the protection of personal data.

Application. A data protection impact assessment is necessary if the use of new technologies and, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, are likely to lead to a major threat to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

Necessity. Data protection impact assessment is necessary especially in the following cases:

- systematic and comprehensive assessment of personal aspects related to natural persons, based on automated processing, including profiling, and on the basis of which decisions are made that create legal consequences for the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;
- extensive processing of data of special categories referred to in Article 9 paragraph 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation; or
- systematic monitoring of the publicly accessible area on a large scale.

The purpose of the data protection impact assessment. The objectives of the data protection impact assessment are as follows:

- describe the processing of personal data;
- assess its necessity and proportionality;
- assess its threats;
- to help deal with threats to the rights and freedoms of natural persons; and
- determine the measures by which to deal with these threats [29].

Criteria for conducting a data protection impact assessment. The Article 29 Working Party has issued Guidelines for Data Protection Impact Assessment (WP 248) [29]. It recommends that nine criteria should be considered when deciding whether to carry out a data protection impact assessment, and that an assessment should be carried out if two or more of these criteria are met.

These criteria are:

- Evaluation or scoring, including profiling and predicting, in particular analysing and forecasting aspects of data subject related to work performance, economic situation, health, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behavior, location or movements.
- Automated decision-making with legal or equivalently significant consequences: processing of personal data for the purpose of making decisions about data subjects that have legal consequences for a natural person or, equivalently, have a significant impact on a natural person.
- Systematic monitoring: processing of personal data used to monitor or control data subjects, including data collection via networks or "extensive systematic monitoring of public areas.
- Sensitive data or highly personal data: This includes special types of personal data defined in Article 9 of the General Data Protection Regulation.
- Extensive processing of personal data. The General Data Protection Regulation does not define what extensive means, although recital 91 provides some guidance. In any case, the Article 29 Working Party

recommends that the following factors be taken into account when determining whether the processing of personal data is extensive:

- a. the number or proportion of the relevant data subjects in the relevant population;
 - b. volume and/or scope of personal data processed;
 - c. duration or continuity of personal data processing;
 - d. geographical scope of personal data processing.
- Matching or combining data sets, for example in the case of data resulting from two or more personal data processing operations with different purposes and/or performed by different controllers in a way that would exceed the reasonable expectations of the data subject.
 - Data of vulnerable data subjects: this type of personal data processing is included in the criteria because the balance of power between data subjects and the controller is more out of place here, which means that it may not be easy for individuals to consent to the processing of their personal data, object to it or exercise their rights.
 - Innovative use or implementation of new technological or organizational solutions, such as the simultaneous use of fingerprint and facial recognition to enhance physical access control.
 - If the personal data processing operations themselves prevent data subjects from using a right or service or contract.

In some cases, however, the controller may find that a data protection impact assessment is needed even in the case of personal data processing that meets only one criterion.

At the same time, the operation of personal data processing may correspond to some of the cases mentioned above and still be an operation in the eyes of the data controller, as a result of which there is unlikely to be a high risk. In such cases, the data controller should provide and document the reasons why it did not carry out a data protection impact assessment and include/register the opinion of the data protection officer.

Responsibility for conducting a data protection impact assessment. The data protection impact assessment is the responsibility of the data controller. The data protection impact assessment may be prepared by someone else inside or outside the organization, but the responsibility for carrying out this task rests entirely with the data controller.

The data controller must also ask for advice from the data protection officer, if the latter is appointed, and the advice given and the data controller's decisions should be documented in the data protection impact assessment.

If personal data is processed in whole or in part by a data processor, the data processor should assist the data controller in performing a data protection impact assessment and provide any necessary information.

Content of the data protection impact assessment. The General Data Protection Regulation stipulates the minimum content of the data protection impact assessment as follows:

- description of planned personal data processing operations and processing purposes;
- assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing of personal data;
- assessment of threats to the rights and freedoms of data subjects;
- planned measures to address threats and to prove compliance with the regulation.

Importance of data protection impact assessment. A data protection impact assessment is a useful tool for data controllers to implement personal data processing systems that comply with the General Data Protection Regulation. For some personal data processing operations, a data protection impact assessment may be mandatory. These impact assessments are adaptable and can be done in different forms, but the General

Regulation on Personal Data Protection sets out the basic requirements for an effective data protection impact assessment. Controllers should consider the preparation of a data protection impact assessment as a useful and positive activity that helps ensure compliance with legal regulations.

The project team shall seek the advice of the data protection officer, when carrying out a data protection impact assessment.

4. Transfer of personal data to third countries. The General Data Protection Regulation contains a restriction on transborder dataflows. This restriction does not apply if the transfer is to a whitelisted country.

Transfers can be made:

- pursuant to a set of Standard Contractual Clauses;
- pursuant to binding corporate rules;
- to an importer who has signed up to an approved code or obtained an approved certification; or
- where otherwise approved by the relevant supervisory authority.

Recommendations. The European Data Protection Board has issued Recommendation on European Essential Guarantees for surveillance measures and a Recommendation on measures that supplement transfer tools to help conduct this transfer impact assessment. The European Commission has also issued an FAQ on the new Standard Contractual Clauses.

Derogations. Transfers are also possible if an individual derogation applies. These derogations allow a transfer if it:

- is made with the data subject's explicit consent;
- is necessary for the performance of a contract with, or in the interests of, the data subject;
- is necessary or legally required on important public interest grounds, or for legal claims;
- is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject;
- is made from a public register; or
- is made under the so-called minor transfer exemption.

Additional data transfer instructions. The European Data Protection Board has issued Guidelines on derogations applicable to international transfers.

Use of binding corporate rules. The General Data Protection Regulation places binding corporate rules on a statutory footing. It will be possible to obtain authorisation from one supervisory authority (subject to approval through the consistency mechanism) that will cover transfers from anywhere in the European Union [30].

5. Notifying the supervisory authority of a breach related to personal data. In the event of a personal data breach, the data controller shall notify the competent supervisory authority of the personal data breach without undue delay and, if possible, within 72 hours of becoming aware of it, unless the breach is unlikely to pose a threat to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

If the supervisory authority is notified later than within 72 hours, the notification shall provide a justification for this [27].

6. Fines. General Data Protection Regulation aims to make data protection an important issue. It establishes an antitrust sanctions regime with fines of up to 4% of global annual turnover or 20 million euros, whichever is greater. A fine of up to 20,000,000 euros or, in the case of an entrepreneur, up to 4% of its global annual turnover of the previous financial year, whichever is greater, may be imposed for a data protection violation. These fines apply to violations of many provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation, including failure to comply with the six general data quality principles or processing without fulfilling the condition of personal data processing.

A limited number of violations will drop to a lower level and therefore fines of up to 2% of global annual turnover or €10 million, whichever is greater [27].

2.5.2 Finnish data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities

1. Finnish privacy legislation. In Finland, the General Data Protection Regulation is supplemented by the Data Protection Act [31] that came into force in January 2019.

Main additional privacy regulations. Main additional privacy regulations [32] in Finland are as follows:

- the Act on Electronic Communication Services, the purpose of which is to ensure the confidentiality of electronic communications and the protection of privacy;
- the Act on the Protection of Privacy in Working Life, which aims to promote the protection of privacy and other rights guaranteeing the privacy in working life, and;
- the Act on the Processing of Personal Data in Criminal Cases and in connection with Maintaining National.

Main objectives of the Data Protection Act. The Data Protection Act specifies and complements the EU General Data Protection Regulation and its national application. The Data Protection Act provides for the appointment, organisation and powers of the supervisory authority in matters of data protection.

The Data Protection Act also stipulates the following:

- the processing of personal data for the purposes of academic, artistic or literary expression;
- the processing of special categories of personal data;
- the processing of personal identity codes;
- certain situations in which the public interest constitutes a legal basis for processing personal data;
- the age limit for offering information society services to a child;
- restrictions of the right of the data subject [33].

2. National derogations. The Data Protection Act [31] includes national derogations with respect to processing of personal data for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, including the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation relating to right of access, right to rectification, right to restriction of processing and right to object. The Data Protection Act also contains specific provisions on processing of personal ID numbers.

3. Data Protection Officer. Data protection officers play an important role in coordinating the processing and protection of personal data in organizations, including research and development activities.

The main requirements for appointing a data protection officer. Both controllers and processors must appoint a data protection officer if:

- they are a public authority;
- their core activities consist of regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale; or
- their core activities consist of processing special category personal data on a large scale).

Data protection officers must also be appointed where required by national law. In Finland, certain entities which are subject to the public interest, such as social welfare and health care service providers, must appoint a data protection officer.

The Data Protection Act provides that a data protection officer may be appointed as a measure to safeguard data subjects' rights when processing sensitive personal data or personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences.

The Data Protection Act does not provide any exemptions to this obligation [34].

Duties of the data protection officer. The data protection officer is an expert within the organization who oversees the processing of personal data and advises on compliance with data protection regulations.

Data Protection Officer:

- monitors compliance with data protection rules throughout the organization and highlights any deficiencies;
- provides management and employees processing personal data with information and advice on the tasks stipulated in the data protection regulations;
- advises on conducting a data protection impact assessment and monitors its execution;
- is the contact person for data subjects in matters related to the processing of personal data; and
- is the contact person with the office of the data protection ombudsman and cooperates with the office [35].

Instructions for organisations that have designated a data protection officer. In Finland, instructions have been given to organizations that have appointed a data protection officer.

In June 2024, the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman announced the publication of updated instructions for organizations appointing a data protection officer [36]. The Ombudsman emphasized that the data protection officer must be an independent position with adequate resources and cannot be fired or punished for performing personal data protection tasks.

The Ombudsman particularly emphasized that the data protection officer:

- must be independent and have no conflict of interest with his/ her duties;
- should have access to sufficient resources to perform tasks and access to training;
- should participate in handling data protection issues at an early stage;
- should have access to all relevant information enabling appropriate advice;
- must be present at the adoption of decisions affecting data protection;
- should have clearly defined and written responsibilities that are communicated to the employees of the organization; and
- should report directly to senior management and be invited to regular senior or middle management meetings.

The Ombudsman stated that the determination for purposes and means of processing personal data must remain with the controller and not become the responsibility of the Data Protection Officer [37].

Most important principles. The following are the most important principles for the activities of the data protection officer:

- It is important that the organisation must cooperate with the data protection officer in building an appropriately comprehensive and independent role for the officer.
- The data protection officer must be guaranteed the necessary resources for the proper performance of his/ her duties, including time, means and competence.
- Regarding the Finnish instructions, it is important to point out that the data protection officer should have a deputy, because the notification of a breach related to personal data and the fulfilment of the data subject's rights must not be delayed due to the absence of a data protection officer.
- The data protection officer shall be involved in the handling of all questions related to data protection at the earliest stage possible.
- It is important from the point of view of the data processing organization that the data protection officer must be given all relevant information without delay so that he can provide appropriate advice. The data protection officer should always be present when making decisions affecting data protection.
- The data protection officer's duties and obligations should be defined clearly and in writing, and the organisation's personnel must be informed of them.
- The data protection officer must have the possibility to report directly to senior management. The data protection officer shall be regularly invited to high- and mid-level meetings.
- The opinion of the data protection officer must always be given due weight. In case of disagreement, the reasons why the data protection officer's advice was not followed should be documented.
- The data protection officer must be consulted as soon as possible if a personal data breach or other issue concerning data protection is detected.
- Data protection officers are not personally responsible for infringements of the General Data Protection Regulation. Compliance with data protection regulations is the responsibility of the controller or processor.
- The data protection officer must be independent and may not have conflicts of interest in their duties as data protection officer. Because each organization is unique, such conflicts of interest must be examined on a case-by-case basis. A data protection officer cannot be in a position where he is required to determine the purposes and means of personal data processing, as this is the responsibility of the data controller.
- The data protection officer may not be given instructions on how to fulfil his duties. A data protection officer cannot be fired or punished for performing data protection tasks [36].

The need to update the instructions. These instructions highlight the most important issues related to the position and role of the Data Protection Officer. In the updated guidance, organizations are reminded of the independent position of the data protection officer and the need for resources.

The update of the instructions is based on the report on the status of data protection officers published by the European Data Protection Board in January 2024. According to the report, many data protection officers still face challenges in carrying out their duties. To respond to the identified challenges, the report makes recommendations to strengthen the position of data protection officers [38].

4. National supervisory authority. In Finland, the national supervisory authority referred to in the General Data Protection Regulation is the Data Protection Ombudsman, who works in the administrative branch of the Ministry of Justice.

The main activity. The Finnish Data Protection Ombudsman and their Office act as the national data protection authority and as the national supervisory authority under the General Data Protection Regulation. The Ombudsman is supported by two Deputy Data Protection Ombudsmen that have equivalent powers with the Ombudsman. In addition, the Data Protection Act provides for establishment of an Expert Board to give opinions on the law at the request of the Ombudsman [34].

Duties of the Data Protection Ombudsman. The main duties of the Data Protection Ombudsman include the following:

- supervision of compliance with data protection legislation;
- promotion of awareness related to the processing of personal data;
- conducting investigations and inspections;
- imposition of administrative penalties for personal data violations;
- issuing statements about legislative and administrative changes related to personal data processing;
- receiving reports of personal data breaches;
- processing requests for the rights of data subjects and notifications of violations related to the processing of personal data;
- receiving declarations of Data Protection Officers [39].

5. Specific legislation. In addition to general data protection legislation, Finland has specific legislation on the processing of personal data. Most of such legislation deals with the processing of personal data by public authorities. Specific legislation either establishes more precise provisions on the processing of personal data in a certain area or specifies how personal data may be processed as an exception to the general legislation.

Specific legislation is divided into legislation dealing with personal data files that play a major role in the functioning of society (e.g. the population register and registers related to the right to study and education) and legislation stipulating the processing of personal data in a specific field (e.g. the Act on the Protection of Privacy in Working Life and the Credit Information Act). Individual data protection provisions can also be found in legislation on other matters [40].

Protection of personal data in employment relationships. Act on the Protection of Privacy in Working Life [41]. The purpose of this Act is to promote the protection of privacy and other fundamental rights safeguarding the protection of privacy in working life.

The main objectives of the Act. This Act stipulates the following requirements:

- provisions on the processing of employees' personal data;
- requirements for the conduct of employee tests and examinations and related requirements;
- conditions of technical surveillance at the workplace; and
- requirements for searching and opening e-mails of employees.

General requirements for collecting personal data. The employer collects the employee's personal data primarily from the employee himself or herself. In order to collect personal data elsewhere, the employer must obtain the employee's consent. However, this consent is not required if the public authority discloses the information to the employer to enable it to fulfil a statutory duty, or if this is expressly provided for in the data collection or acquisition law.

Necessity requirement. The employer is only allowed to process personal data directly necessary for the employee's employment relationship. Such data are related to the management of the rights and obligations of

the parties to the employment relationship or the benefits provided by the employer to the employee, or arise from the specific nature of the work in question.

No exceptions can be made to the necessity requirement, even with the employee's consent.

Personality and aptitude assessment. With the consent of the employee, he or she can be tested with a personality and aptitude assessment to determine his ability to work or the need for training and other professional development. The employer ensures that the assessment methods used are reliable, that the persons conducting the assessment are experts and that the conclusions of the assessment are error-free.

Camera surveillance requirements. The employer may use a continuous surveillance system (camera surveillance) based on the use of technical equipment that transmits or records images in its premises to:

- to ensure the safety of employees and other persons in the premises;
- to protect property;
- to supervise the proper functioning of production processes; and
- to prevent or investigate situations that threaten safety, property or the production process.

Video surveillance may not be used:

- in toilets, changing rooms or other similar places;
- in other staff rooms or in work rooms intended for the personal use of employees;
- to monitor a specific employee at the workplace.

However, the employer may direct camera surveillance to a specific workplace where the employee is working, if monitoring is essential:

- to avoid an obvious threat of violence related to the employee's work or visible damage or danger to the employee's safety or health;
- for the prevention or investigation of property crimes, if an important part of the employee's work is the handling of high-value or high-quality property; or
- for the protection of the employee's interests and rights, if camera monitoring takes place at the request of the monitored employee.

The Act on Electronic Communications Services. According to the Act on Electronic Communications Services [42], monitoring the content of employees' electronic communications is generally prohibited. The monitoring of traffic data is subject to strict conditions.

6. Processing of special types of personal data. According to the Data Protection Act [31], special types of personal data may be processed during specified activities, if certain procedures are met. The processing of special types of personal data is also permitted for scientific or historical research or statistical purposes.

7. Data Processing for Scientific Purposes. According to Data Protection Act [31], Chapter 2, Legal basis for processing in certain cases, Section 4 Lawfulness of Processing, P 3 and 4 –

Personal data may be processed in accordance with point (e) of Article 6(1) of the General Data Protection Regulation if:

- the processing is necessary for scientific or historical research purposes and it is proportionate to the aim of public interest pursued; or

- the processing of research material and cultural heritage material containing personal data and the processing of personal data included in their metadata for archiving purposes is necessary and proportionate to the aim of public interest pursued and to the rights of the data subject.

8. Special instructions for processing personal data in research. Some instructions on the processing and protection of personal data in research activities have been published on the Finnish supervisory authority's – the Data Protection Ombudsman website. In particular, the use of personal data in research activities is emphasized as follows.

Taking care of data protection increases trust in data subjects and is a condition for the success of any research. Data protection regulations protect the rights of data and research subjects. The purpose of the legislation is to find a balance between the protection of personal data and the need to process personal data for research goals. The data protection regulations contain special processing rules and exceptions for scientific research. Special instructions are designed to support and promote research.

A special research plan can often indicate that personal data is being processed for scientific research purposes.

In legal practice, the requirements for publishing personal data for the purpose of scientific research are established as follows:

- existence of an appropriate research plan;
- availability of sufficient scientific qualifications of the project staff;
- compliance with autonomy and openness requirements; and
- setting the main scientific goals of the research [43].

Data protection roadmap for scientific research. A data protection roadmap for scientific research guides data controllers in taking data protection into consideration at the different phases of research and the lifespan of data. This data protection roadmap includes the following steps:

- Defining the research scheme and purpose of personal data processing;
- Minimizing the processing of personal data.
- Lifetime planning of personal data processing, implementation of data protection principles and ensuring data protection.
- Choosing the basis for personal data processing and ensuring the legality of the processing.
- Implementation of the data subject's rights.
- Identification of roles and responsibilities for personal data processing.
- Check of the legal basis for the possible transfer of personal data outside the EU or EEA (transfer of data abroad).
- Demonstrating compliance with data protection legislation.
- Destruction, anonymization or archiving of materials at the end of the research.
- Ensuring familiarity with data protection methods and requirements [44].

9. Obligation to report data breaches. In November 2023, the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman announced that it had published guidance on data breach reporting obligations on its website. The ombudsman noted that the guide was prepared based on feedback from organizations. About half of the cases that reach him are reports of data security violations of personal data [45].

Additional guidance on personal data breaches. The Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman has updated the instructions on its website for submitting personal data breach notifications. These instructions for organizations deal with assessing the severity of the impact on the data subject, informing the data subjects, supplementing the notification and meeting deadlines.

The data controller must notify the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman of a personal data breach if it may cause a threat to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Organizations can submit a data breach notification via the online form of the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman.

- The notification of a personal data breach must address:
- Assessment of the seriousness of the personal data breach for the data subject.
- Notifying data subjects always, even after high-risk violations have been eliminated.
- Submitting a preliminary notification to the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman and then supplementing it on your own initiative.
- Submitting a personal data breach notification within 72 hours, adding an additional description of the incident if necessary [46].

10. Sanctions for violation of personal data protection. Section 9 of the Criminal Code [47] stipulates the punishment for data protection offence as follows. A person who, in a capacity other than that of a controller or a processor referred to in General Data Protection Regulation; intentionally or through gross negligence:

acquires personal data in a manner that is incompatible with their purpose, discloses personal data, or transfers personal data in violation of a provision on the purpose limitation, disclosure or transfer of personal data laid down in the General Data Protection Regulation, the Data Protection Act, the Act on the Processing of Personal Data in Criminal Matters and in Connection with Maintaining National Security, or another act concerning the processing of personal data; and thus violates the protection of privacy of a data subject or causes a data subject other damage or essential harm –

shall be sentenced for a data protection offence to a fine or to imprisonment for at most one year.

A person who intentionally or due to gross negligence violates the security provisions of personal data processing is also punished for a data protection offence.

Fines. The Ombudsman may impose a conditional fine in certain cases, such as failure to comply with the Ombudsman’s right to receive information and right to conduct inspection. On the basis of the Data Protection Act, administrative fines may not be imposed, including state and local government institutions and independent public entities [34].

Imprisonment. In order to ensure the priority of the administrative fines stipulated in the General Data Protection Regulation, the previous data protection violation was replaced by a more limited data protection crime in the Finnish Criminal Code. This most likely applies to the misuse of personal data by company employees.

A crime is committed by a natural person who does not process personal data as a responsible processor or authorized processor and collects, publishes or transmits personal data intentionally or due to gross negligence, in violation of:

- the principle of purpose limitation or the provisions of the transfer or disclosure of personal data under the General Data Protection Regulation and other laws related to personal data and thereby violates the privacy of the data subject or causes material damage or other harm; or
- mandatory data security requirements.

The crime is punishable by a fine or up to one year in prison [34].

2.5.3 Estonian data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities

1. Estonian privacy legislation. In Estonia, the General Data Protection Regulation is supplemented by the Personal Data Protection Act [48] that came into force in January 2019.

Goal. The Personal Data Protection Act helps implement the General Data Protection Regulation into Estonian law. The Personal Data Protection Act entered into force on 15 January 2019.

Scope of the Act. The Personal Data Protection Act regulates:

- the protection of natural persons in the processing of personal data to the extent that it clarifies and supplements the provisions contained in General Data Protection Regulation;
- the protection of natural persons in the processing of personal data by law enforcement authorities in the prevention, detection and prosecution of crimes and in the execution of punishments.

The Personal Data Protection Act provides:

- norms to implement General Data Protection Regulation;
- norms to adopt Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council, which deals with the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purpose of preventing, investigating, detecting and prosecuting offenses or enforcing criminal penalties, and the free movement of such data;
- procedures for performing state and administrative supervision over the fulfilment of personal data processing requirements;
- responsibility for violation of personal data processing requirements.

2. National derogations. The concept of administrative fines does not exist in the Estonian legal system.

3. Data Protection Officers. Both controllers and processors must appoint a data protection officer if:

- they are a public authority;
- their core activities consist of regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale; or
- their core activities consist of processing special category personal data on a large scale.

Data protection officers must also be appointed where required by national law. The Personal Data Protection Act does not include any additional mandatory obligation to appoint data protection officers in Estonia.

The Data Protection Inspectorate has published a recommendatory list of knowledge and skills necessary for a data protection officer. In addition, some Estonian higher education institutions offer training programs for data protection officers, including Tallinn University of Technology.

Duties of the data protection officer. The data protection officer must be involved in all data protection matters and cannot be fired or punished for performing his role. The data protection officer must report directly to senior management. The data of the data protection officer must be forwarded to the Data Protection Inspectorate.

The duties of the Data Protection Officer include:

- inform and advise the data controller or data processor and employees processing personal data regarding their personal data processing obligations;
- monitor the fulfilment of the principles of personal data;
- give advice in relation to data protection impact assessment and monitor its operation;
- cooperate with the supervisory authority;
- act as a contact person for the supervisory authority in matters of personal data processing [49].

Fulfilling the role of data protection officer. The role of a data protection officer can be fulfilled by:

- employee of the data processor (e.g. separate position);
- a subdivision of the data processor (e.g. a department) or;
- external legal entity of the data processor (e.g. based on a service contract).

If the duties of the data protection officer are performed by a subdivision of the data processor or another legal entity, the contact for the public and the supervisory authority should still be one specific person with contact details [49].

Knowledge, skills and competences required by a data protection officer. The Data Protection Inspectorate has compiled a list of recommended competencies [49] that are a prerequisite for the effective performance of the role of a data protection officer. As part of the implementation of data protection principles is the ability to implement competent security measures, the data protection officer must also have knowledge of information security principles and related technologies.

Tallinn University of Technology processes data both as a data controller and as a data processor and has therefore appointed a data protection officer. The contact information of the data protection officer is publicly available both on the website of Tallinn University of Technology and in the Estonian e-business register.

The duties of the data protection officer of Tallinn University of Technology are defined in the employment contract and accompanying job description based on the corresponding requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation [50].

4. National Supervisory Authority. The Data Protection Inspectorate will act as the supervisory authority in Estonia.

The Data Protection Inspectorate will represent Estonia on the European Data Protection Board.

The Data Protection Inspectorate is independent in the performance of its tasks and acts based on the Personal Data Protection Act, General Data Protection Regulation, other laws and legislation established on the basis of them.

The data subject's right to appeal to the Data Protection Inspectorate. According to the Personal Data Protection Act [48] § 28. *Data subject's right to address Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate –*

If the data subject finds that his rights are violated in the processing of personal data, he has the right to file a complaint with the Data Protection Inspectorate.

The Data Protection Inspectorate informs the data subject of the decision made on the basis of his complaint and of the right to go to court to contest the Data Protection Inspectorate's decision.

If the competent supervisory authority of another European Union member state is competent to resolve the data subject's complaint, the Data Protection Inspectorate will refer the data subject to the competent supervisory authority of another European Union member state to file a complaint.

5. Special rules for processing personal data of employees. The General Data Protection Regulation allows member states to implement more specific national rules governing the processing of employees' personal data. It may also be possible to process special category personal data if it is necessary to fulfil a legal obligation in the field of employment law.

The Estonian Employment Contracts Act does not stipulate special rules for the processing of employees' personal data. Except § 41 of the Estonian Employment Contracts Act, which states that the employee has the right to:

- get acquainted with the information collected about him;
- request the removal or correction of incorrect data.

The employer ensures the processing of the employee's personal data in accordance with legislation [51].

Specific instructions for processing personal data in employment relationships. The Data Protection Inspectorate has established more specific guideline for the processing of personal data in employment relationships. The Data Protection Inspectorate's guideline "Processing personal data in employment relationships" is a helpful and advisory guidance material for organizations for the processing of personal data in employment relationships [52].

The aforementioned instruction was useful from the point of view of personal data processing and protection of project management.

6. Processing of special types of personal data. There are no additional rules and exceptions regarding the processing of special types of personal data in Estonia. Tallinn University of Technology has discussed with the Data Protection Inspectorate the provision of possible exceptions in the legislation in order to facilitate the conduct of technology-related research and development activities.

7. Processing of personal data for the needs of scientific research. According to the Personal Data Protection Act [48] § 6 *Processing of personal data for needs of scientific and historical research and official statistics* –

Personal data may be processed without the consent of the data subject for the needs of scientific research, in particular in a pseudonymized form or in a form that enables an equivalent level of data protection. Before transferring personal data for processing for the needs of scientific or historical research, personal data is replaced by pseudonymized data or data in a form that allows for an equivalent level of data protection.

De-pseudonymization or any other method by which non-personally identifiable data is changed to personally identifiable is allowed only for the needs of additional scientific research. The processor of personal data designates by name the person who has access to data enabling de-pseudonymization.

For the needs of scientific research, the processing of data about the data subject without the data subject's consent in a form that enables identification of the data subject is permitted only if the following conditions are met:

- after the removal of identifiable data, the purposes of data processing can no longer be achieved or would be unreasonably difficult to achieve;
- in the opinion of the creator of scientific or historical research or national statistics, there is an overriding public interest;
- based on the processed personal data, the scope of the data subject's obligations will not be changed or the data subject's rights will be excessively damaged in any other way.

If a scientific research is based on special types of personal data, the ethics committee of the relevant field will check before fulfilling the conditions set forth in this section. If there is no ethics committee in the scientific field, then the Data Protection Inspectorate checks compliance with the requirements.

For the purposes of this Act, analyses and researches of the executive state power, which are carried out for the purpose of policy making, are also considered scientific research. In order to compile them, the executive state authority has the right to make inquiries into the database of another responsible or authorized processor and to process the received personal data. The Data Protection Inspectorate checks the fulfilment of the conditions set forth in this section before starting the processing of the said personal data, unless the purposes of the study for policy formulation and the scope of the processing of personal data result from legislation.

If personal data is processed for the purpose of scientific research, the responsible or authorized processor may limit the rights of the data subject provided for in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 of General Data Protection Regulation to the extent that the exercise of these rights is likely makes it impossible to achieve the goal of scientific research or significantly hinders it.

8. Guidelines for the processing of personal data in research and development activities. As of January 2019, the scope of the Personal Data Protection Act includes research conducted for the purpose of policy-making and scientific or historical research, which means research conducted for the purpose of research in the sense of the Act on the Organization of Research and Development Activities.

The researcher must first analyse whether and on what legal basis the desired personal data will be collected and processed. If there is no legal basis, personal data may not be collected/ processed for research purposes.

The legal basis for conducting scientific research can primarily be:

- the consent of a person;
- the performance of a task in the public interest (law); or
- in the case of a private researcher, an additional legitimate interest.

In the cases specified in the law, it is necessary to apply for permission to conduct the research. The corresponding permission must be requested either from the ethics committee of the scientific field or from the Data Protection Inspectorate. In certain cases, permission must be requested from both the ethics committee and the Data Protection Inspectorate. Such cases are policy-making research with special types of personal data.

Cases that do not require a permit for scientific research. It is not necessary to apply for a scientific research permit in the following cases.

It is not necessary to apply for permission if personal data is processed in research with the consent of the person. However, in this case, the General Data Protection Regulation applies to the processing of personal data.

It is not necessary to apply for a permit if the research is carried out with anonymous data (ie the person is marked with an identifier that does not allow him to be identified), then this data is not considered personal data in the sense of the law. However, in certain cases, permission to anonymize personal data is required, for example, when the data is anonymized by a person.

The need to apply for permission from the Data Protection Inspectorate. It is necessary to apply for permission if a research containing special types of personal data is carried out in a scientific field where there is no ethics committee. Research conducted with ordinary personal data does not require the permission of the Data Protection Inspectorate, with the exception of policy-making research. It is necessary to apply for permission if the institution conducts a policy-making study and for this purpose requests are made to the database of another responsible or authorized processor or data sets under the responsibility of another responsible or authorized processor are used.

Requirements to be considered when conducting consent-based scientific research. If the research is conducted with the person's consent, the consent form must meet the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation. This means that the consent must clearly define the data for which permission is given, the purpose of the data processing and the persons to whom the data transfer is permitted, as well as the conditions for the data transfer to third parties and the data subject's rights regarding the further processing of his/ her personal data. Silence or inaction does not constitute consent. Consent can be partial and conditional [53].

9. Tallinn University of Technology's data processing and protection guidelines. At Tallinn University of Technology, university members are instructed in issues related to data processing and protection in research activities. The principles of the guidelines for data processing and protection of research activities of Tallinn University of Technology [54] are outlined below. These principles have also been taken into account when processing personal data in the case of the 5G-ROUTES project.

According to the aforementioned data processing and protection guidelines, the processing of personal data is conventionally divided into two types of processing related to research activities:

- Project management data processing. The data of project executors is processed in project management reporting.
- Use of data in research. Processing of personal data related to human habits, behavior, health and the use of technologies.

In the 5G-ROUTES project, personal data related to the work of the project implementers and has been collected.

In the research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, personal data related to the use of technology has been collected.

The legal basis for personal data processing in the aforementioned cases is data protection and scientific legislation.

Personal data related to research activities are data collected from or about individuals, the processing of which is necessary to achieve research goals, including:

- results of experiments/ tests;
- recordings of interviews;
- transcriptions of recordings;
- survey responses;
- location and observation data;
- behavioral and health data;
- measurement results;
- other personal data.

In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, data has been processed in a non-personalized form during the experiments/tests.

The principle of collecting minimal personal data in research. The principle of minimum collection of personal data in research includes the following:

In the case of research, data initially collected for other purposes may be used in subsequent research. A corresponding legal basis is necessary.

According to the principle of minimum, as little data as possible should be collected and processed. Only data necessary to achieve the research objective.

In order to comply with the principle of minimum, it is necessary to consider what specific data are needed to meet the objective.

In the research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, personal data has been collected as minimally as possible.

Storage of personal data for a certain period. Personal data may be stored until the purpose is fulfilled and then deleted or anonymized.

After the original purpose has been fulfilled, personal data may only be retained if the processing is carried out in the public interest for archival, historical or research purposes or for statistical purposes.

Personal data of the administrative activities of the 5G-ROUTES project must be stored in accordance with the retention periods provided for European Horizon 2020 projects. This means that the storage of data is based on the retention periods resulting from the legislation. The determination of retention periods is based on the real professional need, including the performance of audits and inspections.

Incorrect personal data. Incorrect personal data can also be considered personal data.

The principles of personal data protection apply to all personal data, regardless of their accuracy or correctness.

In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project data, it is also important to keep in mind that incorrect information about individuals is personal data.

Legal basis for personal data processing in research activities. The processing of personal data in research is legal if the processing has:

- identified legal basis;
- compliance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation;
- applied data protection principles.

The legal basis for personal data processing must be determined before personal data processing begins.

In the case of research work, the main question is whether the subject's personal data is processed with the consent of the data subject or on another basis.

Processing personal data without consent always requires justification and an appropriate legal basis.

Legality of personal data processing. The processing of personal data is lawful only if there is one of the legal bases specified in the General Data Protection Regulation.

The consent of a person is the most common legal basis for the processing of personal data in research.

The person's consent supports the decision-making ability of the persons involved in the research to participate on a voluntary basis.

The person's consent must be voluntary and informed. There are requirements for asking for consent.

A public interest task is the legal basis for processing for public research organizations operating for the purposes set out in the legislation.

In the administrative activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, the legal basis for the processing of personal data is the employment legislation and the fulfilment of the employment contract.

In the research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, the legal basis for the processing of personal data is the legislation on research and development activities. Consequently, the legal basis for personal data processing is usually the consent of the individual.

Responsibility for data processing in research. Research data is managed by researchers associated with the project or working at the university.

It is advisable to appoint an employee responsible for the data processed in the research, i.e. a responsible researcher who is responsible for managing the data.

The responsible researcher must follow the data protection principles and check that other participants in the project follow them.

The responsible researcher informs the project manager and the data protection officer about any violation of data protection requirements during the project.

In the case of 5G-ROUTES, the appointment of persons responsible for (personal) data processing has also been a relevant recommendation.

The need for data protection is constant in research. Data protection must be addressed throughout the research, from the pre-study and early stages –

If project data needs to be pseudonymized for security reasons, this should be planned as early as possible in the project. For example, how to anonymize, who has access to the key or data and what is done with the key at the end of the project.

As data protection issues overlap with data management issues, it is advisable to address both at the same time. For example, data protection issues and topics can be written into a data management plan.

In the activities of the 5G-ROUTES research and development project, the issue of data protection has been taken into account in different stages of the project.

Systematic data management and protection. Systemic data management and protection is important in research projects. Systematic data management has become commonplace and may be required by research funders, including grants from:

- the Horizon Europe;
- the European Research Council and;
- the Estonian Research Agency.

Since the data management plan provides a systematic overview of all collected and analysed data, it is reasonable to combine this activity with an overview of the processing of personal data in research projects.

In the case of the activities of the research and development project 5G-ROUTES, the issues of data processing and data protection have been systematically approached.

Tools for systematic data management protection. Systematic data management and protection tools include the following:

- Research control questionnaire;
- Checklist for the processing of personal data in research;
- Data management plan;
- Data protection impact assessment.

The research control questionnaire is useful to use when planning the research. The checklist for the processing of personal data in research helps to identify what is important regarding the processing and protection of personal data. Both tools have found use in a more or less official and conscious form in the case of the 5G-ROUTES project.

Data management plan. The data management plan raises and answers the following questions:

- How is the data planned to be collected/ received?
- What are the data types?
- How are the different types of data related?
- What data formats are used?
- What is the amount of data?
- What software is used?
- Where, how and for how long is the data stored?

In the case of the data management of the 5G-ROUTES project, attention has been paid to the aforementioned questions.

Benefits of a data management plan. The data management plan helps to describe the data in order to make it:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable and
- Reusable

in the interests of open science.

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable is FAIR principle.

The FAIR principle has also been an important principle to follow in the data processing of the 5G-ROUTES project.

In addition, the data management plan helps to identify in a timely manner the possible obligations and requirements associated with the processing of personal data.

For example, a data management plan provides an overview:

- of what part of the data is personal data;
- whether special types of personal data are processed;
- whether data already collected for other purposes are used;
- how the confidentiality and integrity of the data is ensured and;
- with whom the data is shared.

Attention has been paid to the aforementioned questions when specifying the personal data processing of the 5G-ROUTES project. A data management plan is a good starting point for identifying potential data protection issues.

A data management plan may be mandatory for researchers, as it is often required by research funders, including Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research grants.

In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, the data management plan has been implemented in different stages of the project.

The need for data protection impact assessment. People's rights and interests can be protected through a data protection impact assessment.

A data protection impact assessment is necessary if data processing poses a serious threat to human rights and interests.

If a researcher considers that an impact assessment may be necessary for a proposed research, they should contact the Data Protection Officer.

In the case of cooperation projects, it should be agreed separately which partners are responsible for conducting the data protection impact assessment and how other partners will be involved.

In the case of transnational projects, it is useful to discuss and agree in advance how and who will carry out the data protection impact assessment.

10. Specified requirements for data protection impact assessment in Estonia. The Data Protection Inspectorate's "General Guideline for Personal Data Processors" [55] specifies the need for a data protection impact assessment. A data protection impact assessment must be carried out by all personal data processors who, given the nature, scope, context and purposes of their personal data processing, are likely to pose a high risk to people. When defining the obligation to carry out a data protection impact assessment, the criterion is the systematicity and extensiveness of the processing. According to the Data Protection Inspectorate's "General Guidelines for Personal Data Processors", systematic data processing is planned and methodical. Data processing is extensive if it includes special or criminal data on 5,000 or more people, or high risk data on 10,000 or more people, or other personal data on 50,000 or more people. In the case of cross-border data processing, extensive processing is not defined by a precise minimum number of data subjects.

In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, the possibilities of conducting a data protection impact assessment have been outlined and explained in the project's previous guidance materials.

11. The need to notify of a data protection breach. The Data Protection Inspectorate's "General Guideline for Personal Data Processors" [55] specifies the reporting of data protection violations. The data controller shall notify the Data Protection Inspectorate without undue delay, if possible within 72 hours after becoming aware of the breach, which caused or is likely to cause a threat to data subjects.

Even if all the reasons for the violation are not yet known, or if it is not definitively clear, for example, the number of persons affected by the violation, the initial notification should still be made within 72 hours. This gives the Data Protection Inspectorate the opportunity to assess the nature of the violation early and provide feedback and recommendations to the data processor if necessary.

If additional circumstances appear, the data processor will forward them as a follow-up notification without undue delay. The data processor must justify why it was not possible to provide all the circumstances regarding the violation in the initial notification. If the authorized processor of personal data detects a violation, it informs the data controller without undue delay, who in turn notifies the supervisory authority.

The breach notification sent to the Data Protection Inspectorate must contain:

- a description of the nature of the violation related to personal data. This can be, for example, loss or destruction of data, theft, making a copy. Also unauthorized modification, reading or transmission;
- if possible, the categories of relevant data subjects and their approximate number and the types and approximate number of relevant records of personal data;
- the name and contact details of the data protection specialist or other contact person;
- a description of the possible consequences of a violation related to personal data;
- a description of the measures to resolve the breach related to personal data, including, if necessary, mitigating the possible adverse effects of the breach.

The Data Protection Inspectorate has prepared a more detailed form of a breach notification with multiple choice answers. The form is available on the website of the Data Protection Inspectorate.

If, as a result of the breach, there is likely to be a major threat to people's rights and freedoms, the controller must also inform the data subject without undue delay. The purpose of the notification is, in addition to the data processor, to enable the data subject himself to take the necessary precautions to mitigate the risk (for example, to change the password). The notice should describe the nature of the personal data breach, as well as provide recommendations for mitigating the potential adverse impact. The notification delivered to the person must include:

- the nature of the personal data breach explained in clear and simple language;
- the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact person;
- a description of the possible consequences of a personal data breach;
- description of measures to resolve a personal data breach [55].

Specific notice of breach laws apply to the electronic communications sector under national laws implementing the Privacy and Electronic Communications Directive and to operators of essential services and digital service providers under national laws implementing the Network and Information Systems Directive.

In Estonia data controllers in certain sectors may be required to inform sectoral regulators of any breach (for example, financial services firms may be required to inform the Financial Supervision regulator) [51].

In the administration, research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, there were no situations where it would have been necessary to inform the Data Protection Inspectorate about a violation of the project's data protection requirements.

12. Requirements for transferring personal data to third countries. The Data Protection Inspectorate's "General Guideline for Personal Data Processors" [55] presents the following principles for the transfer of personal data to third countries. When transferring data outside the European Economic Area, it must be observed whether it is a country with an adequate or insufficient level of data protection. The list of third countries with an adequate level of data protection is available on the European Commission's website. When transferring personal data to a third country with an insufficient level of data protection, protective measures according to Article 46 of the General Data Protection Regulation must be applied.

Article 49 of the General Data Protection Regulation regulates exceptional cases in which personal data may be transferred to a third country without applying the corresponding protective measures. Detailed rules for forwarding to third countries are not discussed in this "General Guideline for Personal Data Processors". This information is available on the website of the European Commission, as well as on the website of the European Data Protection Board [55].

In the 5G-ROUTES project, attention was paid to the possibilities of transferring data to third countries. The issue of transferring personal data to third countries did not arise during the project.

13. Fines. The legal system of Estonia does not allow for administrative fines to be issued based on the powers in the GDPR (as confirmed in recital 151 of the GDPR).

Instead, penalties must be issued under national law, the Estonian Penal Code was amended on 1 November 2023 to allow for larger penalties under other laws. The Personal Data Protection Act allows a maximum penalty of EUR 20,000,000 or up to 4 percent of its total global annual turnover for the previous financial year, whichever amount is higher (which is an increase in the previous maximum penalty of EUR 400,000). The Data Protection Inspectorate also has the authority to impose the fines using the criminal misdemeanour procedure [51].

Fines for violation of personal data processing requirements and data subject's rights. According to the Personal Data Protection Act [48], the possible fines imposed on the personal data processor are as follows:

- **Violation of principles of personal data processing.** For a violation of the principles of personal data processing provided for in Article 5 of General Data Protection Regulation, as well as for a violation of the procedure for granting the data subject's consent provided for in Articles 5–7 and 9 of the aforementioned regulation, shall be punished with a fine of up to 20,000,000 euros.

For the same act, if it is committed by a legal entity, shall be punished by a fine of up to 20,000,000 euros or up to 4 percent of its total global annual turnover of the previous financial year, whichever amount is the higher.

- **Violation of data subject's rights.** Violation of the rights of a data subject provided for in Articles 12-22 of General Data Protection Regulation, shall be punished with a fine of up to 20,000,000 euros.

For the same act, if it is committed by a legal entity, shall be punished by a fine of up to 20,000,000 euros or up to 4 percent of its total global annual turnover of the previous financial year, whichever amount is the higher.

2.5.4 Latvian data processing, protection and privacy legislation, rules and procedures related to research, development and innovation activities

1. Latvian privacy legislation. In Latvia, the General Data Protection Regulation is supplemented by the Personal Data Processing Law that came into force in July 2018 [56].

Goal. The purpose of this law is to create the legal prerequisites for the creation of a system for the protection of personal data of a natural person at the national level establishing the institutions necessary for this purpose, determining the basic principles of competence and its operation, as well as the provisions regulating the activities of data protection officers and data processing and free movement.

2. National derogations. The Data Protection law provides that in certain situations specific provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation will not apply, including:

- the rights of data subjects under the General Data Protection Regulation for the processing of personal data for scientific or historical research purposes in the interests of general public can be limited in certain circumstances where the application of the rights is likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the objective of that processing;
- the General Data Protection Regulation does not apply to cameras used for road traffic purposes (i.e. dash-cameras). However, it is prohibited to share such data with third parties, except state institutions for the fulfilment of their legal functions and to other controllers for the protection of their legitimate interests. The Data Protection Law will also not apply to CCTV cameras if they are used by natural persons for personal or household reasons, except where cameras survey public areas on a large scale or where technical aids are used for structuring of information [57].

It was important to pay attention to the above-mentioned points, i.e. the processing of personal data in research activities and the use of cameras, in view of the research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project.

3. Data Protection Officers. The Data Protection Law provides further details on the appointment of a data protection officer. In order to work as a data protection officer, a person can pass the examination procedure established by the Data State Inspectorate, which certifies the data protection officer's compliance with General Data Protection Regulation requirements. The Data Protection Law also allows data controllers to select another

person who has not passed the Data State Inspectorate exam and appoint him or her as a data protection officer, provided that he or she meets the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation [57].

Duties of the data protection officer. The data controller or data processor may appoint a person who, in accordance with the procedures laid down in the Personal Data Processing Law [56], has been included in the list of data protection officers of the Data State Inspectorate, or another person as the data protection officer.

For the purpose of identifying data protection officers who have passed the qualification examination and ensuring that information regarding data protection officers is accessible, the Inspectorate shall compile a list of data protection officers. The list of data protection officers shall only include the persons who have passed the qualification examination.

The list of data protection officers is publicly available on the website of the Data State Inspectorate.

Requirements for the Data Protection Officer. The Data Protection Law does not specify any additional mandatory obligation to appoint data protection officers. However, the Data Protection Law provides additional details about the appointment of a data protection officer. In order to serve as a data protection officer, a person can pass an examination procedure set up by the Data State Inspectorate, which certifies that the data protection officer meets the GDPR requirements. The Data Protection Law also allows controllers to choose another person, who has not taken the Data State Inspectorate exam, and appoint him or her as a data protection officer, provided that he or she meets the GDPR requirements [57].

4. Data Protection Inspectorate. The Data State Inspectorate is an institution of direct administration under the supervision of the Cabinet which is a data supervisory authority within the meaning of the General Data Protection Regulation and carries out the tasks in the area of data processing specified in the General Data Protection Regulation and the Personal Data Processing Law.

The aim of the operation of the Data State Inspectorate is to protect fundamental human rights and freedoms in the area of data protection. The Data State Inspectorate is independent in its activities [56].

5. Data Processing for Scientific Purposes. If data are processed for scientific purposes in the public interest, the rights of a data subject specified in Articles 15, 16, 18, and 21 of the General Data Protection Regulation shall not be applied, insofar as they may render impossible or seriously impair achievement of the specific purposes, and derogations are necessary for the achievement of such purposes [56].

6. Video Surveillance Conditions. Requirements of the Personal Data Processing Law and the General Data Protection Regulation shall not apply to data processing which natural persons conduct by using automated data recording facilities in road traffic, for personal or household purposes. It shall be prohibited to disclose the records obtained in road traffic to other persons and institutions, except for the cases when any of the grounds for data processing specified in the Data Protection Regulation is present.

If the controller uses an informative note to inform data subjects of video surveillance, the said note shall indicate at least the name, contact information of the controller, purpose for data processing, as well as include an indication of the possibility to obtain other information specified in Article 13 of the General Data Protection Regulation [56].

7. Special rules for the processing of personal data of employees. The General Data Protection regulation allows Member States to implement more specific national rules governing the processing of personal data about employees. It may also be possible to process special category personal data where it is necessary for a legal obligation in the field of employment law.

National laws permit processing of the following types of data in an employment relationship:

- processing relating to enforcement of rules regarding admissible job interview questions, and
- processing in relation to an employer's duty to ascertain employee membership in a trade union prior to giving notice on termination of employment contract.

Furthermore, an employer cannot process employee personal data related to criminal convictions except in situations where the law regulating the employee's specific position allows for such processing. In addition, an applicant has a duty to provide information to the employer regarding the state of their health if it may impact their possibility to carry out the work [57].

8. Processing of special types of personal data. The Data Protection Law does not introduce any specific national conditions for processing of special types of personal data, however there are general derogations on the application of the General Data Protection Regulation and these may also relate to sensitive data processing [57].

9. Notice of breach laws. Local guidance on breach notifications have been published by the Data State Inspectorate. The guidance provides concise clarifications on how the notice must be provided to the authority. Additionally, a notice of breach form has been published by the Data State Inspectorate, which can be used to notify the Data State Inspectorate in relevant circumstances. The use of the form is not mandatory when notifying the Data State Inspectorate [57].

10. Imprisonment. Latvian criminal law provides that an individual who has committed criminal acts involving personal data may be punished by imprisonment for up to 5 years, probationary supervision, community service or fine. Criminal liability can be imposed where data has been processed:

- illegitimately and resulted in material damage;
- for the purpose of vengeance, acquisition of property or blackmail; or
- using violence, threats or in bad faith, or using deceit in order to perform illegal activities involving personal data [57].

2.6 Chapter summary

This chapter provided an overview, description and analysis of the legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to the 5G-ROUTES project. In the process, it was reviewed, described and analysed that:

- research and development activities were legally sound;
- during the conduct of research and development, attention was paid to legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to the research project;
- the processing of research data was based on the relevant legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to the research project;
- the legislation, regulations, rules and procedures in the field of fundamental human rights, artificial intelligence, cyber security, telecommunications, data processing, data protection and privacy were taken into account in connection with the research project.

The main legal topics were related to research, technology and data protection legislation. European Union and national legislation determined the main frameworks within which the project was implemented.

During the implementation of the project, legal issues were treated as unambiguously as possible. It was important that the project partners treat the legal framework as uniformly as possible. For this purpose, European and national legislation on research, technology and data processing was reviewed, analysed and introduced to the project partners during consortium meetings.

It was also important to define use cases and tests as precisely as possible, taking into account specific European Union and national legal requirements. Regarding use cases and tests, the legal background of the use cases, the data processing, personal data processing and possible human participation were reviewed. Use case leaders, in cooperation with experts in the field of law and data protection, monitored their implementation in accordance with the requirements. Use cases and tests have taken place in accordance with European Union and national legal requirements.

In the case of the research work, the main theme was to conduct it according to the established rules. Fulfilling the requirements of European projects was an important aspect here. The conduct of this research had to meet the requirements stipulated in the project conditions, which in turn are based on the requirements of Horizon 2020. Based on the monitoring of the project execution and regular feedback evaluations of the project supervisors, the project has taken place in accordance with the European Horizon 2020 requirements.

It was also important to comply with technological and security requirements. Adherence to technological conditions affected the implementation and results of the project. Regarding the information security of the project, it was recommended that the partners of the consortium involve information security experts in case of information security issues. Security requirements defined by cyber security legislation have been implemented.

Complying with data processing and protection requirements was an important aspect of conducting the research. The fulfilment of the project's data, personal data processing and protection requirements has been followed by experts in the field of data processing and data protection of the consortium partners. There were no violations of data protection security requirements during the implementation of the project. The activities of 5G-ROUTES have taken place in accordance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union and national legislation.

In the project implementation stage, artificial intelligence was limited to machine learning algorithms and technical processing of sensors in a small number of use cases, rather than processing or interacting with humans. A further challenge requiring attention at a general level may be related to the development of artificial intelligence, its wider use and the implementation of relevant legislation in the future.

3 Ethics principles, policies and procedures in research, development and innovation activities

3.1 European Union Horizon 2020 research ethics principles and policies

Considering ethics in research. In the case of activities funded by the European Union, ethics is an integral part of the research from the beginning to the end. Ethical compliance is considered central to achieving true excellence in research.

Applying ethics to research. Ethical research requires the application of the basic principles of ethics and legislation in scientific research in all possible fields of research. In addition to scientific evaluation focusing on scientific value, management quality and potential impact, ethics evaluation ensures that all research activities carried out within the framework of the Horizon 2020 Framework Program are carried out in accordance with the basic principles of ethics.

In order to ensure trust in science, the European Commission considers it important to fulfil ethical requirements [58].

Horizon 2020 ethics legislation. The legal background of Horizon 2020 ethics is as follows:

- Horizon 2020 – Regulation of Establishment: Ethical principles (Article 19);
- Horizon 2020 Rules for Participation: Ethics Reviews (Article 14);
- Model Grant Agreement: Ethics (Article 34) [59].

Aspects of research ethics. The broad topic of research ethics is discussed from different aspects:

- Research integrity;
- "Ethics ready" proposals;
- Ethics monitoring during project implementation;
- Funding of ethical research;
- Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) [59].

Research integrity. Research integrity is a more general level aspect that must be considered when conducting any kind of research and development.

The Model Grant Agreement of Horizon 2020 states that the beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with:

- ethical principles, including the highest standards of research integrity. In particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct; and
- applicable international, European Union and national law [59].

Principles of research integrity. The principles of integrity in scientific and scholarly research are the following:

- honesty in communication;
- reliability in performing research;
- objectivity;
- impartiality and independence;
- openness and accessibility;

- duty of care;
- fairness in providing references and giving credit; and
- responsibility for the scientists and researchers of the future [59].

"Ethics ready" proposals. In the case of "Ethics ready" proposals, both the research and development project customer and the research and development project executor have a role to play.

Ethics monitoring. Ethics monitoring in the case of a research and development project is the responsibility of both the project customer, executor and independent party.

Funding of ethical research. Funding of ethical research is based on relevant policies developed at a higher level.

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a specific set of principles for conducting ethical research.

Responsible Research and Innovation means that societal actors work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes, with the values, needs and expectations of European society.

Responsible Research and Innovation is a cross-cutting issue of Horizon 2020:

- engagement of all societal actors;
- gender equality;
- science education;
- ethics;
- open access;
- governance [59].

During the research and development activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, attention has been paid to the aforementioned aspects of research ethics principles.

Responsibility for ethics requirements. In the European Horizon, great responsibility for meeting ethical requirements is placed on scientists and researchers. It is assumed that applicants for funding are able to perform a corresponding ethical analysis, and corresponding instructions have also been prepared.

At the same time, this responsibility is not only on the shoulders of scientists and researchers, but institutions and the national level must have created structures and systems that enable and support the fulfilment of ethical requirements [59].

Potential ethical issues. In the case of cooperation projects, cultural differences and legal requirements must be taken into account, both in the European Union and in the wider world. These differences, for example between disciplines and cultures, are not in themselves a problem for research cooperation, if they are dealt with sufficiently proactively and transparently [59].

It is important to emphasize that in the case of an international research and development project like 5G-ROUTES, it has been essential to take into account different disciplines and cultures in the activities. Various cultural differences and legal requirements have been taken into account in the 5G-ROUTES project.

3.2 Ethical requirements arising from the research activities of the 5G-ROUTES project

5G-ROUTES sought to accelerate Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) acceptance. The aim was to ensure fully autonomous, safer, cleaner, traffic-efficient, user-friendly and reliable mobility and to provide seamless and uninterrupted interoperable cross-border CAM services. 5G-ROUTES took the scope for large-scale CAM field trials of the strategically important Via Baltica-North 5G EU corridor. It was planned to include road, rail and sea transport modes in Estonia, Finland and Latvia. The 5G-ROUTES project has carried out advanced field trials of representative and innovative Connected and Automated Mobility applications that operated seamlessly in a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North'), therefore spanning across 3 European Union member states borders (Estonia, Finland, Latvia). The objectives were:

- validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions;
- accelerate the widespread adoption of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services on digitized highways, railways and waterways across Europe.

The aim was to validate 5G as a true enabler of innovative CAM services that cannot be realized by today's wireless communication technologies due to strict technical requirements.

This was initially sought to be achieved through a set of 13 different use cases that extend beyond C-ITS to include the automotive, infotainment, transport and logistics sectors, including shipping, which are expected to have the greatest commercialization and social potential.

The use cases were originally grouped into 5 categories:

- automated cooperative driving;
- awareness driving;
- sensing driving;
- uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go; and
- multimodal services.

These included applications in the context of complete connectivity-enabled ecosystems surrounding passengers and cargo.

The use cases were planned in one phase combined with road transport and in the second phase with multimodal transport, including shipping. For this, the 5G-ROUTES consortium has collaborated with various actors. In the 5G-ROUTES project, the ethical requirements resulting from the ethical screening report indicated the possibility of involving people in the research process and personal data processing during the project. For this, appropriate procedures, criteria and informed consent forms were prepared for potential human participants. Procedures regarding the protection and privacy of personal data processed during the project were also prepared. In the case of 5G-ROUTES, the involvement of individuals was seen in human participation in terms of events, meetings, interviews and surveys, where personal data is collected, as well as various testing (test-beds/ use cases). In the above cases, the procedural rules of data protection were applied to the processing of personal data. During the research, the aim was to process the data in an aggregated form.

3.3 Ethics principles and rights, their adoption and application

Ethics principles and rights and their application. The research activities of the 5G-ROUTES project respect the following principles and rights:

- the principle of proportionality;
- the right to privacy;

- the right to the protection of personal data;
- the right of all persons to physical and mental integrity;
- the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination.

Special attention is paid to the principle of proportionality when conducting research activities. The principle of proportionality has been important in the view of the participants of the 5G-ROUTES project.

The principle of the right to privacy has to be observed from the point of view of the persons conducting the research and development project and possible research subjects.

The principle of the right to privacy is closely related to the principle of the right to personal data protection, which has to be ensured in the processing of personal data of 5G-ROUTES research and development activities.

The right of all persons to physical and mental integrity must be considered both for persons conducting the 5G-ROUTES project and for persons directly or indirectly related to it.

The principles of environmental protection and human health protection have also had to be taken into account in the research activities of 5G-ROUTES. The participants of the 5G-ROUTES project value both the environment and human health.

For innovative approaches and activities, the European Commission recommends using the "ethics by design" methodology. The 5G-ROUTES project has taken this "ethics by design" methodology into account.

Adopting the principles of ethics. The partners of the 5G-ROUTES consortium have adopted the main principles of ethics and compliance with relevant national, European Union and international legislation.

Value areas to monitor. For the structure of the six value areas of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [3], three have required monitoring in 5G-ROUTES project:

- Dignity, in particular the right of individuals to be protected with regard to their physical and mental integrity.
- Freedoms, which include the right to data protection and privacy, as well as intellectual freedoms (freedom of education, speech, thought, religion and information) and social freedoms (assembly and property);
- Equality, including non-discrimination and the rights of minorities and socially vulnerable parties.

Research integrity principles to monitor. The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [60], which contains the principles of research integrity, has required monitoring of the following principles:

- Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, which is reflected in design, methodology, analysis and use of resources;
- Integrity in developing, conducting, peer-reviewing, reporting and reporting research in a transparent, fair, complete and unbiased manner;
- Respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
- Responsibility for research from idea to publication, its management and organisation, training, guidance and mentoring and its wider impact.

Personal responsibility of researchers. It is the personal responsibility of researchers to conduct their research based on good research practices. Good research practice must follow the context described in the Code of Conduct in Research integrity. It covers the following components:

- Research procedures;

- Research environment;
- Training, coaching and mentoring;
- Cooperation;
- Data practices and management;
- Safeguards;
- Publication and dissemination;
- Reviewing, Evaluation and Editing [60].

Safeguards for researchers. For individual researchers, it is important to be aware of the following safeguards:

- comply with codes and regulations related to their discipline;
- treat research subjects, whether human, animal, cultural, biological, environmental or physical, with respect and care and in accordance with legal and ethical provisions;
- take due account of the health, safety and welfare of the community, collaborators and others involved in the research;
- consider sensitivity to differences in age, gender, culture, religion, ethnicity and social class in research protocols;
- recognize and manage potential harms and risks associated with research.

During the procedures or planning stage of a research project, the researcher must examine possible ethical issues in the research plan and take steps to improve them.

The proposed research plan and its implementation must undergo an ethical assessment beforehand. If an ethical problem exists, the researcher must change the plan. If the research plan meets the ethical conditions, the researcher can start or move to the next phase.

Ethical researchers must address issues of explicit and informed consent, confidentiality, safety, fraud, debriefing, security, and diversity in research involving human subjects. It is the researcher's job to think through these questions to find out if the participants experience any of these questions and perhaps react negatively to it [60].

3.4 Ethical aspects of data processing, protection and privacy and their application

Ethical aspects of privacy. In addition to national and European Union legislation, 5G-ROUTES researchers have followed:

- relevant ethical guidelines and rules regarding data handling and storage;
- informed consent procedures; and
- participant recruitment criteria at their institution.

The implementation of the General Data Protection Regulation has significantly raised the level of demonstrating compliance with ethical principles.

The general purpose of ethics principles and policies is to ensure compliance with ethical requirements. One important component of meeting ethical requirements is related to the processing and protection of personal data during the 5G-ROUTES project.

The right to data protection is a fundamental right stated in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [3]. This means that the processing of personal data of the 5G-ROUTES project partner has had to comply with the applicable data protection law.

External inputs shaping ethical requirements have mainly been the General Data Protection Regulation, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and the European Union Responsible Research and Innovation policy [61].

Compliance with the European values set out in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [3] includes the right to data protection and privacy, in Articles 7 and 8 as follows:

- Respect for private and family life: Everyone has the right to have their private and family life, home and communication respected.
- Protection of personal data:
 - Everyone has the right to the protection of their personal data.
 - Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and with the consent of the person concerned or on any other legitimate basis provided by law. Everyone has the right to consult the data collected about him and the right to request their correction.
 - Compliance with these regulations is monitored by an independent body.

In the activities of the 5G-ROUTES project, there was no impact/ violation of private communication or other aspects of family life.

Data management is covered in D5.7 ("Data Management Plan v1.0") and D5.8 ("Data Management Plan final version") as part of T5.3 – Innovation, Data Management and Intellectual Property Rights activities.

The data management plan has followed the proposed principles as described in this deliverable. The data management plan has defined the management strategies to be implemented during the project's data processing procedures.

The data management plan is continuously updated with decisions on the categories of data to be shared within or outside the consortium and their chosen formats. It is based on the use of information and personal data created and obtained during the project.

3.4.1 Personal data processing and protection requirements and implementation

In connection with the protection of personal data, the following measures to ensure the compliance of personal data protection were established in the 5G-ROUTES project:

- Information sheets;
- Informed consent forms;
- Informed consent procedures;
- Confirmations from partners' data protection officers/ responsible persons to ensure proper data processing and protection.

From an ethical perspective, privacy is the protection of a person's own physical, mental and behavioral sharing. Confidentiality is how researchers handle participant information and ensure that private information or other types of data are not disclosed without the participant's written consent. This includes handling information disclosed by an individual in a relationship of trust and provided that it is not disclosed to others without permission or in a manner inconsistent with the understanding of the original disclosure.

Personal data may only be collected for a specified period in accordance with data protection legislation. In certain cases, it must be possible to delete personal data at the request of the data subject who participated in the research.

Important aspects of data processing and protection that are addressed in informed consent forms include the following:

- Purpose of data collection, storage and research;
- Categories, types and composition of data;
- Data ownership;
- Data transfer and communication;
- Data connection with personal data and separate storage;
- Commercial use of data;
- Duration of data storage;
- Data accesses and access restrictions;
- Data security measures;
- Data supervision.

Personal data processing and protection. The General Data Protection Regulation [27] defines as personal data any information related to an identified or identifiable natural person (data subject).

An identifiable natural person is a person who can be directly or indirectly identified, in particular by reference to an identifier such as:

- a name;
- an identification number;
- a location data;
- an online identifier; or
- one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that individual.

Thus, the scope of personal data is broad, including anything that allows a person to be uniquely identified, such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or one or more factors characteristic of that person's physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.

Some personal data are special types of personal data related to sensitive aspects of the personality of natural persons, including:

- Genetic data: personal data related to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person;
- Biometric data, which are data obtained during specific technical processing related to a person's physical, physiological or behavioral characteristics;
- Health data related to a person's physical or mental health, including the provision of health care services;
- Data reflecting racial or ethnic origin;

- Data about political views;
- Data describing religious or philosophical beliefs; and
- Data concerning sex life or sexual orientation.

The processing of special types of personal data is generally prohibited and may only be processed in certain specific cases.

The aforementioned special categories of personal data are subject to additional protection as they are considered to be a core part of the protection afforded to individuals by privacy regulations.

When processing personal data, the General Data Protection Regulation includes a number of requirements, restrictions and controls that govern how personal data should be collected, stored, processed and shared.

When processing personal data, the Personal Data Protection Regulation includes a number of requirements, restrictions and controls that govern how personal data should be collected, stored, processed, stored and shared.

The most important requirements, restrictions and controls are as follows:

Consent of the data subject. The consent of the data subject is required to collect personal data. It is important to emphasize that consent by default is not valid. The organization seeking consent will also provide clear information about how this data will be used, how long it will be stored and how it will be shared with third parties. Individuals may withdraw consent at any time without limitation. If the data is used for processing outside of the initial consent, additional permissions must be requested from the individual.

Data protection officer. The data protection officer is appointed in the cases provided for in Article 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation [27].

Data protection impact assessment. Organizations conduct internal assessments to understand the risks associated with personal data. General Data Protection Regulation [27] article 35 defines the circumstances in which a data protection impact assessment is mandatory. According to Article 35 of the GDPR, each partner has assessed whether the processing of personal data is likely to pose a significant risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing. A data protection impact assessment is necessary when an organization processes personal data in a way that is likely to cause a high risk to an individual's rights and freedoms. Data protection impact assessments are mandatory in a number of processing scenarios where an organization makes automated decisions based on personal data profiling, large-scale processing of special categories of data or systematic large-scale monitoring of publicly accessible areas.

Among other things, a data protection impact assessment is required if the organization:

- Uses systematic and extensive high-impact profiling; or
- Processes a large amount of special category data; or
- Systematically monitors publicly accessible places on a large scale.

All partners have monitored whether a formal data protection impact assessment was necessary due to the nature of the research activity. If necessary, partners have consulted the project's data protection officer for guidance.

Data protection by default and by design. Data protection must be by default and by design, requiring data protection mechanisms to be embedded in products and services from the earliest stages of development and the adoption of the strictest privacy settings without manual input from the end user.

Partners have been asked to comply with Article 5 of the General Data Protection Regulation [27] that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and transparently in relation to the data subject;
- are collected for specified, explicit and lawful purposes and are not further processed in a way that is incompatible with those purposes. Further processing for scientific research is not considered incompatible with the original purposes;
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes of their processing;
- accurate and, if necessary, updated. All reasonable steps must be taken to ensure that personal data that is inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which it is processed, is deleted or corrected without delay;
- is stored in a form that allows data subjects to be identified no longer than is necessary to achieve the purposes of personal data processing. Personal data may be stored for a longer period of time, insofar as personal data are processed solely for scientific research purposes. Appropriate technical and organizational measures are implemented. measures required by this regulation to protect the rights and freedoms of the data subject ("recording restriction");
- processed in a way that ensures adequate security of personal data, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organizational measures. Appropriate technical and organizational measures are implemented;

The data controller is responsible for proving compliance and fulfilling the reporting obligation.

Rights of individuals. The rights of individuals are guaranteed. Individuals must have easier access to their data, allowing them to see what data is held about them and how it is processed, with whom it is shared, and the ability to migrate that data between service providers without restrictions.

Profiling and automated decision-making. Profiling and automated decision-making must ensure the rights of data subjects for profiling. The data subject has the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which leads to legal consequences for that person or affects that person with other impactful consequences. Automated processing and profiling is permitted if the decision is:

- necessary for the conclusion or performance of the contract between the data subject and the data controller;
- with the Union or Member State law applicable to the data controller and which also provides for appropriate measures to protect the rights and freedoms and legitimate interests of the data subject; or
- based on the explicit consent of the data subject.

In case of automated processing and profiling, the data controller shall implement appropriate measures to protect the rights and freedoms and legitimate interests of the data subject.

Reporting a data protection breach. Data protection breach must be reported to the data protection authority. In the event of a data breach, it is stipulated that within 72 hours the notification of the breach must be forwarded to the data protection supervisory authority. This allows appropriate corrective actions to be taken and individuals to be notified when necessary. The procedures and requirements for notification in the event of a data protection violation have been as follows:

- The project participant immediately informs the data protection officer of his institution and the project about the data breach.
- The data protection officer informs the data protection supervisory authority of the data breach within 72 hours.

- The data protection officer shall immediately take appropriate measures to remedy the data breach and to find out the circumstances of the incident.
- If necessary, the data protection officer will contact the data subjects whose personal data is affected by the data breach [27].

Purpose and minimality of data processing. Personal data processed for any purpose or purposes shall not be stored longer than is necessary for that purpose or purposes. The main requirement has been that the personal data generated or obtained during the project is destroyed as soon as possible after the achievement of the specific goals to which the data are related. The data is planned to be stored as long as necessary and in no case longer than 3 years after the end of the project. If a project member finds that certain data needs to be stored for longer than 3 years after the end of the project, he/she will coordinate this with the data protection officer. Data is stored in a secure environment. The appropriate environment for data storage is decided by the project members in consultation with the data protection officer.

In the case of deletion of project data, it has been agreed in advance that the data will be deleted as soon as possible after the end of the need to use the data. When deleting data, it is planned that the data will be securely deleted by overwriting it using special software. The decision to delete data and appropriate software is given to project members in consultation with the data protection officer.

Protection of personal data. The data processor implements appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks, including encryption of personal data. Personal data is not stored centrally, without anonymization or pseudonymization if necessary. Corresponding software solutions suitable for project participants have been used for data encryption. The use of a suitable technical solution for data encryption has been up to the project members, taking into account the recommendations of information security experts.

The aforementioned requirements have been taken into account in the research ethics principles and procedures of the 5G-ROUTES project.

In general, only aggregated or anonymized data is processed. It was technical data created, generated or obtained during the research process. In the case of the data of the persons who participated in the research process, procedures have been applied to extract the data enabling identification and profiling.

If the processing of personal data has been necessary for specific reasons, the interested 5G-ROUTES project partner has remained responsible for the data collected during its research and has followed European and national privacy and data protection regulations as well as ethical principles and procedures.

Designation of the partner data protection officer. In accordance with the Horizon 2020 data protection and ethics rules, the project partner involved in the collection and/ or processing of personal data has appointed a data protection officer prior to the data collection/ processing. A data protection officer must be appointed in any case if:

- The processing is carried out by a public authority or body;
- The core activities of the data controller or the data processor consist of processing operations which, by virtue of their nature, their scope and/or their purposes, require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale; or
- The core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9 of the General Data Protection Regulation [27].

The data protection officer has, among others, the following duties:

- Informing and advising the data controller or data processor and their employees who fulfil their data protection obligations;
- Monitoring compliance with European Union and national data protection regulations, including assigning responsibility and raising awareness and training relevant staff;
- In the case of consulting, consultations related to data protection impact assessment and compliance and performance monitoring;
- Cooperation with the supervisory authority;
- Acting as a point of contact for the supervisory authority in matters related to processing [27].

3.4.2 General ethical aspects of scientific data processing and protection and their application

General data management. During the research project, it has been important to carefully consider and document the methods of data collection and processing.

In the process, it has been important to specify:

- who is responsible for the data;
- who has access to project data;
- what happens to the data after the project is completed.

The data management plan has described the procedures that have been followed during the project. The optimal time for data storage is 3 years after the end of the project.

The principles proposed in the data management plan procedures are listed below as follows:

1. Data acquiring, including:

- 1.1 Self-collecting;
- 1.2 Re-using previously collected data;
- 1.3 Public (Open) Data collecting;
- 1.4 Re-using data collected by others;
- 1.5 Buying data.

2. Data description, including:

- 2.1 Data types;
- 2.2 Data integration;
- 2.3 Data preservation;
- 2.4 Data permissions.

3. Data formats, including:

- 3.1 Data formats choice explaining;
- 3.2. Using open formats;
- 3.3 Using standard formats;

3.4 Using Machine-readable formats;

3.5 Recommended data formats.

4. Data volume, including estimating the data volume at the end of the project: preservation, access, backup, data exchange, hardware and software, technical support, expenses.

5. Data creation and collection methods and procedures, including:

5.1 Naming the existing standard procedures and methods;

5.2 Available data standards;

5.3 Ensuring data quality (availability, integrity, confidentiality);

5.4 Errors handling (input errors, problematic values).

6. Software.

7. Organisation of Data:

7.1 Systematisation;

7.2 Folder and file organisation;

7.3 Cloud-based code repository;

7.4 Metadata.

Project data confidentiality. Due to the requirements of transparency and general benefit of the European Horizon 2020 research and development project activities, the data of the project results may be freely publicly available in the future. During the project, data has been considered potentially confidential and made available only on a strict need-to-know basis. Therefore, the data is adequately protected against access or use by unauthorized persons. The grant agreement has defined rules for non-disclosure of confidential information in the project.

3.5 Ethical aspects of artificial intelligence

Ethical issues related to artificial intelligence. The importance of artificial intelligence (AI) in research and development is increasing. This means that artificial intelligence has to be addressed in various possible research and development aspects.

The analysis of ethical issues related to artificial intelligence in research activities means that the activities that include development and deployment as well as the use of systems or techniques based on artificial intelligence must be considered. Their technical durability and safety must also be demonstrated.

Important principles in analysing the ethics of artificial intelligence solutions. In the case of artificial intelligence solutions that are developed and/ or used, the following must be taken into account:

People need to be informed that they are interacting with an AI system. People must be informed about the possibilities and limitations, risks and benefits of the system. The self-assessment must describe how this is done.

Mechanisms for human supervision, transparency and auditability must be built into the artificial intelligence system. An AI system must be designed to avoid biases in input data and algorithms. The analysis must explain what methods are intended to be used to avoid possible prejudice, discrimination and stigmatization.

During the development phase, it must be checked that the algorithm does not shift. Also, in the development phase, deviations that can make the system work unequally for different end users must be avoided. The design of the interface must be such that universal access is ensured.

Unethical applications should be avoided. Such examples can be, for example, the violation of physical and mental integrity, the creation of addiction, the risk of damaging social processes and public institutions (for example, contributing to disinformation).

Ethical experts take into account the assessment of technical robustness when making ethical judgments. Technical robustness refers to the technical aspects of AI systems and development, including attack resistance and security, overall safety, accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility [62].

Artificial Intelligence Guidelines. Artificial intelligence topics are regulated by law in the European Union. In addition, the European Commission's expert group has developed many different guidance materials, including:

- Ethics guidelines for trustworthy artificial intelligence;
- Guidelines for the Ethics of Design/Operational Use of Artificial Intelligence;
- EU White Paper on Artificial Intelligence [62].

3.6 Gender perspective

Gender perspective. Gender equality concerns all parts of the Horizon 2020 framework program. Attention must be paid to gender equality based on the following aspects:

- Human resources – balance between women and men in the research groups implementing the project;
- Content – analysing and taking into account possible differences between men and women, boys and girls or men and women in the research and innovation content of the project [63].

Horizon 2020 encourages the promotion of gender balance in teams and management structures at all levels. Participants should aim to achieve a balanced participation of both men and women in teams and leadership roles as close to 50/50 as possible.

It is important to consider the gender dimension as much as possible. Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation adds value in terms of excellence, creativity and business opportunities. It helps researchers to question gender norms and to rethink stereotypes, standards and reference models. This leads to a thorough understanding of the needs, behaviors and attitudes of both sexes. This increases the societal importance of the knowledge, technologies and innovations created. It also contributes to the production of goods and services better suited to potential markets [63].

The gender balance principles of research groups have sought to include:

- Balanced representation of genders in research and development activities to the greatest extent possible and in management structures and research groups;
- “Collective Intelligence”, which means that no gender dominates the other;
- Balanced representation in decision-making.

The grant agreement stipulates that grant beneficiaries take measures to implement equal opportunities for men and women. Beneficiaries must, where possible, strive to achieve gender balance at all levels of staff involved in the measure, including supervisory and management levels.

The 5G-ROUTES project has included significant female representation. Several work packages have been led by women. Women have significant representation in the project management board. Several tasks have been managed or (co-)managed by women, and prominent roles have been filled by women, including project manager and quality manager.

The 5G-ROUTES project consortium was committed to creating and maintaining a work environment that promotes gender equality and clearly prohibits discrimination. The 5G-ROUTES project teams have supported equal career opportunities.

For the 5G-ROUTES project, the importance of gender/ sex has been reviewed in relation to the different expectations that men and women may have regarding 5G-ROUTES innovation. In the innovations, attention has been paid to the gender dimension, the needs, motivation and differences of women and men.

The current status of the gender distribution of the organizations participating in the project according to the number of male and female employees involved in the project is as follows:

- Airbus Defence and Space GmbH: 2 male and 1 female;
- CTTC: 6 male and 2 female;
- Cumucore: 3 male;
- EDI: 6 male and 1 female;
- EEE: 3 male and 2 female;
- ENIDE: 7 male, 4 female;
- INLECOM: 5 male, 5 female;
- SWARCO: 7 male and 1 female;
- TTU: 7 male and 1 female;
- VEDIA: 7 male and 1 female;
- VTT: 13 male and 5 female;
- WINGS: 3 male and 1 female.

3.7 Research ethics framework, principles and policies and their application

3.7.1 Research ethics framework, principles and policies

Research ethics framework, principles and policies. The ethics framework, principles and policies of the 5G-ROUTES project have been defined and refined during the project. It is based on European research ethics legislation, instructions and guidance materials. Based on this, the relevant guidances, tools and countermeasures of the 5G-ROUTES project, adopted by the project consortium to ensure ethical compliance, have been identified.

The more general purpose of the ethics tasks of the 5G-ROUTES research and development project was to ensure that the innovation accompanying the project was in line with European ethics and moral values.

This was ensured by applying the theory of Value-Sensitive Design. Value-Sensitive Design theory is an approach that aims to integrate a wide range of human and moral values into the design of information technology.

The first step was to create a normative ethics framework for the 5G-ROUTES project and derive specific ethical requirements based on this framework. It was then possible to assess to what extent the 5G-ROUTES project already met and which requirements deserved special attention in the future.

The grant agreement stipulates that beneficiaries must implement the measure in accordance with:

- ethical principles, including the highest standards of research integrity;

- with applicable international, EU and national legislation.

According to the grant agreement, beneficiaries must ensure that:

- persons performing research tasks follow good research practice and refrain from violating the integrity of the research work;
- the activity of the measure focuses exclusively on civilian applications.

3.7.2 Ethics management safeguards, identification and mitigation of ethical risks and the tools used for this purpose

Ethics management safeguards. In order to ensure compliance with ethical principles, the 5G-ROUTES project has established several safeguards, including:

- The 5G-ROUTES project has defined research ethics principles and policies to guide project activities.
- The 5G-ROUTES project has determined the coordination of scientific ethics principles and policies. Ethics topics are monitored by the Legal and Ethics Leader of the project (TTU) in cooperation with the involved legal advisors and participating members (experts on ethics and data protection issues). The role of the Legal and Ethics Leader of the project and the legal advisors involved in the cooperation and the participating members (ethics and data protection experts) have been tasked with monitoring the ethical requirements of the project to ensure its compliance with ethical standards. In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, those experts and specialists who support the adherence to ethical principles and policies have been proposed. The project partners have appointed their ethics and data protection representatives in the project. It included experts and specialists in ethics, privacy and legal matters from participating members. The above-mentioned panel of ethics experts has been ready to advise and monitor the compliance of the project's activities with the principles and policies of scientific ethics. This has also ensured a critical assessment of the legal and ethical issues arising from the project's activities.
- As an external advisor, it has been possible to involve the Academic Ethics Committee of Tallinn University of Technology and its experts as needed.
- In addition, it has been possible to involve independent experts in the field from outside the project participants. This is important to get an alternative opinion and view on project activities and results.
- The 5G-ROUTES consortium has implemented the research project in compliance with international and national ethical requirements and guidelines. The adoption of the aforementioned requirements and guidelines has shaped the project's own principles and procedures. This has meant that the execution of testing and use cases and experiments has been assessed based on legal and ethical requirements and guidelines and taking into account project principles and procedures.

Identification and mitigation of ethical risks and the tools used for this purpose. The procedure or process of scientific research may involve certain ethical risks. An important part of risk assessment is the future participant's perception of the significance of the risk. A participant in scientific research can be significantly influenced by the perception of risk.

Relevant legislation, regulations and codes of ethics have been taken into account when identifying and mitigating ethical risks.

Risk assessment tools. In order to assess ethical risks, the project has used special ethics control and assessment forms, including the Ethics checklist form and the Ethics controlling report template (Annex I).

Informed consent forms. The end point of the process of participation in scientific research is the consent given by a person to participate in a research project, having previously considered all aspects of the process and asked

all relevant questions. It is necessary to provide all relevant information to research participants. This means that there is a need to explain the project and its goals. The administration of informed consent has ensured that the participant agrees to participate and is informed about the project and its goals. Written consent is obtained after informing the participants. The information provided is clear and comprehensible about the aims and methods of the research, its duration and participation, confidentiality, safety and risk issues, and the role of the participants and their and their benefits in the project.

Key elements of 5G-ROUTES informed consent have included:

- Purpose, duration and methodology of the research;
- Possible risks, inconveniences and side effects;
- Privacy and data protection procedure;
- The ability to refuse the offer and withdraw at any point in the process without consequences;
- Identification of data controllers and data processors;
- Information about data controllers, authorized processors and data management in general;
- Contact details and persons.

Proportionality of data use. In order to avoid risks related to the processing of personal data, such as identity theft, discriminatory profiling or continuous monitoring, the principle of proportionality has been followed. The data has been used only for the original purpose for which it was collected.

Anonymizing or pseudonymizing data has been a way to prevent violations of privacy and data protection rules. Processing has been limited to what is truly necessary and less intrusive means have been considered to achieve the same goal. The project has determined which data protection rules apply and compiled a list of risks and possible solutions; taking due account of the following:

- What data is processed?
- What is the purpose of the processing?
- Does the data exceed the purpose of the research?
- Who owns the data?
- Is the data linked to other information?
- Is the data used commercially?
- What is the data retention period?
- Where is the data stored and according to which national legislation?
- Who can access the data? Are they secured?
- Is the user saved?
- What metrics are applied?
- Who will supervise data protection?

Recruitment principles. When recruiting external research participants, the following guiding principles are set as a basis:

- Participation is voluntary and participant can withdraw from research at any time;
- Recruitment corresponds to the research question and methods; and

- Participants will be selected in a non-discriminatory manner.

Voluntary participation. It has been up to the participant to decide whether or not to participate in the activity.

Research methods. Research integrity is based on good research practices. By ensuring a good research environment, greater trust in researchers has been achieved. In this way, researchers are better engaged with the practical, ethical and intellectual challenges inherent in their research. Therefore, the basic principles of research integrity have been important recruitment criteria for 5G-ROUTES, including reliability, honesty, respect, accountability.

In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, the principles of research integrity were ensured by introducing specific research practices in order to:

- improve the research environment;
- stimulate training, coaching and mentoring;
- promote open, transparent and non-discriminatory investigation procedures;
- stimulate cooperation;
- report results for publication and dissemination.

Non-discrimination. The implementation of non-discrimination is based on the principles of the respective human rights.

Recruitment procedures. The general rule for the recruitment of research participants was that they were identified and selected by the use case leaders. In the case of participant recruitment, it was envisaged that, if necessary, participants would be recruited by the use case leaders from their respective networks for the defined purposes. The procedures listed in the following paragraphs have been followed to respond to the identified risks and obstacles.

Participation in the activities of the 5G-ROUTES project has been completely voluntary. Potential participants have the opportunity to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making decisions about participation.

Informed consent process. In the ethics principles and procedures of the project, it is specified that the potential participant must give explicit consent to the collection of personal data before being involved in the project's activities. The consent of the data subject is a specific, informed and unambiguous notification voluntarily given by the data subject, by giving which or by a clear affirmative action, he/ she expresses his/ her consent to the processing of personal data related to him/ her. According to the conditions related to consent, consent must be given by a clear affirmative act, which gives a voluntary, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's consent to the processing of personal data concerning him/ her. Consent may be given by written statement, including by electronic means, or by oral statement. Consent is not just a simple form or document for an individual to fill out and sign. Consent is first and foremost a process involving an individual and an entity that has the right to collect and manage data. The most important aspect of the informed consent process is unequivocally ensuring that the individual is informed in a comprehensive language and that the individual effectively understands the research activities, the use of the data and the potential risks of harm.

Based on the above, the following conditions have been taken into account in the process of informing the participants of the project activities:

- Ensuring the specificity of consent;
- Translation of the consent form into the participant's native language to avoid ambiguity, misunderstanding and risk of misunderstanding;

- In order to reduce the risk of access to information, submitting a consent form to participants in paper form if possible;
- In order to comply with the principle of privacy by default and to respect the freedom of individuals, the consent form must not offer default controlled answers that may persuade to express specific opinions and trigger pure acceptance behavior of participants;
- Respecting people's freedom, carrying out the information and understanding phase, ensuring the necessary time to make the right decision and consequently to sign or not sign the consent form.

Informed consent forms and information sheets have been prepared for potential recruited participants. The informed consent process has been previously developed and presented, with various informed consent templates and information sheets attached. The informed consent process for recruitment has been an integral part of the ethical principles and policies of the 5G-ROUTES project.

In the appendices of this report, the informed consent and information sheet forms are presented.

Withdrawal. Potential participants have the option to withdraw from the research at any time. The communication of this information to participants is provided by means of an information sheet.

Reimbursement. In the case of the 5G-ROUTES project, the pre-agreed principle was that all potential participants are unpaid volunteers.

Responsibility of the person responsible for the use case. According to the privacy, transparency, confidentiality, risk assessment principles of 5G-ROUTES, it was the responsibility of each person responsible for use cases to explain the following to potential research recruits:

- General scope of the 5G-ROUTES project and a brief reference to its objectives;
- Scope and brief description of the test/ use case and corresponding research;
- The value of participation. Explaining the benefits of participating in the project;
- Risk assessment. The biggest risk identified was related to unrealistic hopes and expectations of personal benefits from automated and advanced mobility.

Non-discrimination procedures. The prevention of discriminatory outcomes before the research activity (i.e. during the selection of participants) and after (i.e. during the dissemination and use phase) has been supported by the enforcement of all necessary measures.

Its purpose has been to protect groups and individuals from potential stigmatization based on gender, race, religion, sexual orientation, political beliefs, ethnicity and other social characteristics.

5G-ROUTES had set out to recruit through inclusive, clear, accessible and transparent procedures:

- women (aiming for a ratio of women to men as close as possible to 1:1);
- people from different backgrounds.

It was also defined that any exclusionary practices, marginalization, devaluation of research and creation of stereotypes are unacceptable.

Ensuring a good understanding of the procedures. To ensure that the participants understand the information correctly and effectively, the 5G-ROUTES project partners have had to prepare the following conditions for each project activity involving people:

- Create customized procedures and protocols;
- Ensure that potential participants are fully informed and do not feel pressured, coerced, threatened or stressed by researchers;

- Ensure that participants have prompt access to relevant information about the nature, results and conclusions of the research;
- Provide all information (verbal, written or recorded) in a language and manner fully understood by the participants;
- Make it clear that participation is voluntary and that everyone has the right to refuse participation and withdraw their participation or data at any time without consequence;
- Describe the aims, methods and consequences of the research, the nature of the participation and the resulting benefits, risks or inconveniences;
- Report what procedures will be applied in case of unexpected or accidental findings;
- Provide participants with contact information for researchers so that they can contact the project consortium for information and to decide whether they wish to join.

Informed consent form. The informed consent form is composed of two parts:

- the information sheet; and
- the consent form.

Both parts have been distributed to the participants of the project consortium before the start of the activity. The specificity of each activity has required the preparation of an ad hoc customized information sheet and consent form. Therefore, the above-mentioned templates have to be adapted according to the specific activity.

The informed consent form accepted/ signed by the person or his/her legal representative has been kept safe by the activity organizer throughout the duration of the project. Templates for the information sheet and the consent forms designed for the 5G-ROUTES project are provided in the annexes of this report.

3.8 Chapter summary

This chapter has been prepared with the aim of assessing the compliance of the 5G-ROUTES project with ethical requirements. Regarding the ethics of the project's activities, its legal background, principles and procedures in the implementation of the project's activities have been reviewed and evaluated by experts in the field of technology, law, data protection and ethics of the consortium partners. Based on the ethics assessment, the 5G-ROUTES project has been in line with the ethical requirements of the European Union. The choices made by the 5-ROUTES project are ethically justified and in line with the moral values of the European Union.

The processing and protection of personal data related to project participants were defined as ethical challenges before the project. The appointment of responsible persons, the design of principles and procedures in accordance with legislation and instructions have helped to properly ensure the processing and protection of personal data of the 5G-ROUTES project. In the course of the project, the specific details of the processing of personal data and the need for protection were also revealed. The tools that help the processing and protection of data outlined in this report, including the data management plan, control questionnaires and impact analyses are useful recommended tools.

The inclusion of potential human participants in experiments, tests and use cases required attention. Before carrying out the use cases of the project, the involvement of possible external human participants and the processing of personal data have been assessed. Experts from the project's technical, data processing and protection, and ethics fields participated in the aforementioned activities. Since during the implementation of the project activities, it was specified that the regular human participants were the project participants' own staff, this simplified the implementation of the activities. Use cases involving potential external human

participants and the processing of personal data were evaluated in cooperation with the project members and the Legal and Ethics leader before conducting the experiments. The information sheets and consent forms developed for the implementation of the project have been available to the project parties.

4 Conclusions

This document was deliverable D7.8 "Report on legal and ethics monitoring". This report was the result of activities carried out within work package WP7 and specifically task T7.4 "Legal framework, ethics and gender balance".

"Report on legal and ethics monitoring" provided an overview of the monitoring of legal and ethics principles, policies, procedures and processes in the 5G-ROUTES project.

The report outlined the legal and ethical framework related to the implementation of the 5G-ROUTES project. The possible impact of legal and ethical principles, policies, procedures, processes and related risks were also analysed.

The document provided an overview and analyses the legislation, regulations, rules and procedures related to the project. The focus was on legislation, regulations, rules and procedures in the following areas:

- research and development;
- human rights;
- artificial intelligence;
- data processing and protection;
- privacy;
- cyber security;
- telecommunication.

The ethical principles, policies, procedures and processes of the project were outlined in the ethics chapter of the report. In terms of ethics, the requirements and conditions in the ethics guidelines and recommendations and the corresponding principles, policies and procedures in the project were reviewed and analysed.

5 References

References

- [1] European Commission, "Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) and repealing Decision No 1982/2006/EC," 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2013/1291/2015-07-04>. [Accessed 01 05 2024].
- [2] EC, "Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013. 11 December 2013 Laying down the rules for participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)".," 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013R1290>. [Accessed 01 05 2024].
- [3] EC, "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union," 30 03 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:083:0389:0403:en:PDF>. [Accessed 01 05 2024].
- [4] EC, "The Charter of Fundamental Rights, what it covers and how it relates to the European Convention on Human Rights. Why do we need the Charter?," [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/eu-charter-fundamental-rights/why-do-we-need-charter_en . [Accessed 01 05 2024].
- [5] EC, "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2012/C 326/02. Official Journal of the European Union, 26.10.2012, C 326/391," 26 10 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT&from=EN>. [Accessed 01 05 2024].
- [6] EP, "European Parliament. EU AI Act: first regulation on artificial intelligence.," 18 06 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20230601STO93804/eu-ai-act-first-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [7] EC, "European Commission. AI Act. Why do we need rules on AI?," [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [8] EUCO, "European Council. Artificial intelligence (AI) act: Council gives final green light to the first worldwide rules on AI," 21 05 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/05/21/artificial-intelligence-ai-act-council-gives-final-green-light-to-the-first-worldwide-rules-on-ai/>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [9] EC, "European Commission. AI Act," [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [10] "Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Explanatory letter of the Cyber Security Act draft," 26 09 2017. [Online]. Available: https://www.koda.ee/sites/default/files/content-type/content/2017-10/seletuskiri_k%C3%BCberturvalisuse%20seadus.pdf. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [11] EC, "Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2 Directive)," 27 12 2022.

- [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02022L2555-20221227&qid=1720793058999> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [12] EC, “European Commission. Directive on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2 Directive),” [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [13] EC, “Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code,” 11 12 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L1972>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [14] “Finnish Government. Government appoints Research and Innovation Council.,” 23 11 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/en/-/government-appoints-research-and-innovation-council> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [15] “Finnish Government. Research and Innovation Council,” [Online]. Available: <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/en/research-and-innovation-council> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [16] “Ministry of Justice of Finland. Act on Electronic Communications Services,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2014/en20140917.pdf>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [17] Estonian Parliament, “Organisation of Research and Development Act,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/503062019008/consolide/current>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [18] “Ministry of Education and Research. Organisation of Research and Development Act,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.hm.ee/korgharidus-ja-teadus/teadus-ja-arendustegevus/teadus-ja-arendustegevuse-korralduse-seadus>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [19] “Draft of the Organization of Research and Development and Innovation Act,” [Online]. Available: <https://eelnoud.valitsus.ee/main#TbGC9uRP> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [20] “Estonian Parliament. Cybersecurity Act.,” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/519082024019/consolide>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [21] “Estonian Parliament. Electronic Communications Act,” 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/519082024019/consolide>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [22] Latvian Parliament, “Law on Scientific Activity,” 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/107337>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [23] “Latvian Parliament. Electronic Communications Law (Elektronisko sakaru likums),” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://m.likumi.lv/doc.php?id=334345>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [24] “Ministry of Defence Republic of Latvia. Cybersecurity,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.mod.gov.lv/en/cybersecurity>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [25] “Latvian Parliament. National Cyber Security Law (Nacionālās kiberdrošības likums),” [Online]. Available: <https://m.likumi.lv/doc.php?id=353390>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].

- [26] “Latvian Parliament. Law on the Security of Information Technologies (Informācijas tehnoloģiju drošības likums),” 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/220962-law-on-the-security-of-information-technologies>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [27] EU, “Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data,” 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [28] “The Article 29 Working Party. Guidelines on Data Protection Officers (WP243),” 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/612048/en>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [29] EC, “Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) (wp248rev.01),” 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/611236/en>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [30] “Linklaters. Data Protected – Transfer of Personal Data to Third Countries,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.linklaters.com/en/insights/data-protected/data-protected---estonia>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [31] “Finnish Parliament. Data Protection Act (1050/2018),” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2018/en20181050.pdf>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [32] “DLA Piper. Data Protection Laws of the World. Finland,” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dlapiperdataprotection.com/index.html?t=law&c=FI>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [33] “Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman. Data Protection Legislation,” [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/legislation>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [34] “Linklaters. Data Protected – Finland. Data Protection Officers. National Supervisory Authority,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.linklaters.com/en/insights/data-protected/data-protected---finland>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [35] “Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman. Data protection officers,” [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/data-protection-officers>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [36] “Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman. Tietosuojavaaltuutetun toimisto. Instructions for organisations and managers that have designated a data protection officer,” [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/documents/6927448/213374119/Instructions+for+organisations+that+have+designated+a+data+protection+officer.pdf/c91f4d2d-9a54-4f4e-f38b-9d990f08102d/Instructions+for+organisations+that+have+designated+a+data+protection+officer.pdf?t=17>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [37] “Onetrust DataGuidance. Finland: Ombudsman publishes DPO guidance,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dataguidance.com/news/finland-ombudsman-publishes-dpo-guidance>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [38] “Tietosuojavaaltuutetun toimisto. Updated instructions for the organization appointing a data protection officer (Julkaisimme päivitetyt ohjeet tietosuojavaastaavan nimittäneelle organisaatiolle),” 2024. [Online].

- Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/-/julkaisimme-paivitetyt-ohjeet-tietosuojavastaavan-nimittaneelle-organisaatiolle>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [39] "Tietosuojavaltuutetun toimisto. Office of the Data Protection Officer. Duties of the Data Protection Ombudsman.," [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/duties>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [40] "Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman. Data Protection Legislation," [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/legislation>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [41] "Act on the Protection of Privacy in Working Life (759/2004)," 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2004/en20040759.pdf> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [42] "Ministry of Transport and Communications. Act on Electronic Communications Services," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2014/en20140917.pdf>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [43] "Tietosuojavaltuutetun toimisto. Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman. Scientific research and data protection," [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/scientific-research-and-data-protection> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [44] "Tietosuojavaltuutetun toimisto. Defining the research scheme and purpose for processing personal data," [Online]. Available: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/defining-the-research-scheme-and-purpose-for-processing-personal-data>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [45] "OneTrust DataGuidance. Finland: Ombudsman publishes guidance on data breach notification obligations," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dataguidance.com/news/finland-ombudsman-publishes-guidance-data-breach> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [46] "Tietosuojavaltuutetun toimisto. The Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman reminds controllers: Organisations must assess the severity of a personal data breach to the data subjects," [Online]. Available: https://tietosuoja.fi/-/tietosuojavaltuutetun-toimisto-muistuttaa-organisaation-on-arvioitava-tietoturvaloukkauksen-vakavuutta-rekisteroityjen-kannalta?languageId=en_US. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [47] "Criminal Code (39/1889; amendments up to 433/2021 included)," [Online]. Available: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1889/en18890039.pdf> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [48] "The Personal Data Protection Act," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/507112023002/consolide>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [49] "Data Protection Officer (Andmekaitespetsialist). Data Protection Inspectorate," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aki.ee/isikuandmed/andmetootlejale/andmekaitespetsialist> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [50] "Contact information of the data protection officer. Tallinn University of Technology. Estonian e-business register," [Online]. Available: <https://taltech.ee/kontaktid/siseauditi-buroo/henri-schasmin> ; <https://ariregister.rik.ee/eng/company/74000323> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].

- [51] "Linklaters. Data Protected – Estonia. Are there any special rules when processing personal data about employees?," [Online]. Available: <https://www.linklaters.com/en/insights/data-protected/data-protected---estonia>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [52] ""Processing personal data in employment relationships" (Isikuandmete töötlemine töösuhetes). Data Protection Inspectorate," [Online]. Available: <https://www.aki.ee/sites/default/files/documents/2024-04/Isikuandmete%20t%C3%B6%20t%C3%B6tlemine%20t%C3%B6%20suhetes.pdf> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [53] "Personal data in research. Data Protection Inspectorate," [Online]. Available: <https://www.aki.ee/isikuandmed/andmetootlejale/isikuandmed-uuringutes> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [54] "Data processing and protection at Tallinn University of Technology and research activities. Tallinn University of Technology guidelines for data and information processing in research activities," [Online]. Available: <https://taltech.ee/en/privacy-policy>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [55] "General Guideline for Personal Data Processors (Isikuandmete töötaja üldjuhend). Data Protection Inspectorate," 2018. [Online]. Available: https://www.aki.ee/sites/default/files/dokumentid/isikuandmete_tootaja_uldjuhend.pdf. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [56] "Latvian Parliament. Personal Data Processing Law. Legal Acts of the Republic of Latvia," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/300099-personal-data-processing-law>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [57] "Linklaters. Data Protected – Latvia. General – Data Protection Laws. Are there any national derogations?," [Online]. Available: <https://www.linklaters.com/en/insights/data-protected/data-protected---latvia> . [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [58] EC, "European Commission. Funding and Tenders Portal. Horizon 2020 Online Manual. Ethics," [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/ethics_en.htm. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [59] K. Kraav, "Estonian Research Council. Ethics requirements in Horizon2020," [Online]. Available: https://www.etag.ee/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/K_Kraav.pdf. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [60] EC, "European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity," 2017. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/hi/h2020-ethics_code-ofconduct_en.pdf. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [61] EC, "European Commission. Rome Declaration on Responsible Research and Innovation in Europe. Publication 25 November 2014," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/rome-declaration-responsible-research-and-innovation-europe>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].
- [62] EC, "Estonian Research Council. Ethical requirements in the "European Horizon" (Eetikanõuded Euroopa Horisondis)". Ethics Center of the University of Tartu based on the guidelines created by the European Commission," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://etag.ee/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/HE-eetikano%CC%83uded-juhendmaterjal.-Final.pdf>. [Accessed 01 06 2024].

- [63] “European Commission. Funding and Tender Portal. Horizon 2020 Online Manual. Gender equality in Horizon 2020,” [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/gender_en.htm . [Accessed 01 06 2024].

Annex I: Ethics controlling report template

This questionnaire on ethical and legal issues will be filled in by the investigator responsible for conducting trials involving human participants (i.e. **consortium partner leading the testing activity**). The aim is to remind the researcher to consider all relevant ethical aspects before planning and conducting the activity and/or any data collection activities within 5G-ROUTES. The questionnaire is divided into six subsections: General Information, Participants and Informed consent, Ethics control instruments, Privacy, Safety and Risk Management.

Questionnaire on Ethical and Legal issues

A) General information

1. **Name and affiliation (i.e. partner) of the person filling out the report:**
2. **Brief summary of the activity/testing (including type of involvement of human participants):**

Have I obtained approval from my institution's ethics committee and /or other relevant responsible body/authority for the planned testing activities involving human participants?

Yes No

If **yes**, please state by whom:

If **no**, please explain why:

B) Participants and informed consent

3. **Are you aware of the informed consent procedures that relate to your testing?**

Yes No

If **yes**, briefly provide the link to the relevant documents:

4. **Do you intend to conduct testing/pilots with individuals who might not understand the informed consent form?**

Yes No

If **yes**, briefly explain the procedures you follow in order to obtain informed consent:

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

5. **Is there any doubt about the individual's cognitive capacity to consent?**

Yes No

If **Yes**, please clarify who will provide consent in such instance: _____

If **no** please continue with the next question.

6. a) Is the informed consent provided in common language to be understood by a lay person?

Yes No

If **no**, why not? Please provide an example of any *termini technici* used within the description.

b) Will the participant be given sufficient time to reflect his/her decision of giving or withholding consent?

Yes No

If **no**, why not? Please indicate the time given to the participant.

7. Is the participant unable to consent for any reason not specifically listed in questions 2 to 4?

Yes No

If **yes**, no experiment will be performed since these participants are excluded from 5G-ROUTES trials.

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

8. Is the participant for any reason unable to read the form by him-/herself?

Yes No

If **yes**, please continue with b)

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

b) There are a range of people who are unable to read the consent form; these include those who may also have severe visual impairments (e.g. cataract, glaucoma).

9. Have gender balance considerations been taken into account as per the provisions of D7.7 - Legal framework, ethics & gender balance?

Yes No

In **either case**, please briefly explain how and provide relevant information for male/female research participants (how many, type of involvement):

10. Does your experiment include vulnerable participants?

a) in terms of exposure-related vulnerability (e.g. pedestrians, bicyclists, motorcyclists) ?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (number, type of involvement):

b) in terms of non-exposure related disability (e.g. elderly persons, persons with disabilities or other cognitive impairments / learning difficulties)?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (number, type of disability, type of involvement):

11. Are any illiterate foreseen participants?

- Yes No

If **no**, please continue with the question 10.

If **yes**, be advised that an illiterate participant has to provide oral consent which has to be witnessed at least by one person. If that is the case, please name the prospective witness:

Additionally, please answer the following question.

12. Will the oral consent of an illiterate participant that is witnessed be in accordance with your national legislation?

- Yes No

13. Is there an international or national legislation, which you must follow *in relation to the type of testing* you will be within the 5G-ROUTES project involving:

a) human participants in general?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

b) participants with cognitive impairments / learning difficulties or other disabilities?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

c) illiterate participants?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

14. Are there participation incentives other than the expected benefits from the research outcomes that are provided to participants?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details.

15. Will participants receive adequate feedback at the completion of the study, including a debriefing if that is necessary?

- Yes No

In **either case**, please briefly provide details.

C) Ethics control instruments

16. At which level of your organization / enterprise, *ethics controls* are audited?

- laboratory or workgroup
- division or department
- institution
- local/regional
- national

17. Is there an ethics controlling body in your region / country from which you must obtain ethics opinion/permission, other than those that are responsible within the 5G-ROUTES consortium?

- Yes
- No

If **Yes**, please provide details about the body relevant for you and the procedure that has to be adhered to in order to obtain ethical approval of experiments:

18. Is there an established ethics control procedure which you must follow before performing tests with:

a) human participants in general?

- Yes
- No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

b) human participants with cognitive impairments / learning difficulties or other disabilities?

- Yes
- No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

c) *illiterate* participants?

- Yes
- No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

D) Privacy

19. Is personal/private information recorded?

- Yes
- No

20. Is there an established Data Protection Authority issuing procedures / standards you must follow before performing tests with human participants and their personal / private data?

- Yes
- No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain briefly what corrective actions you will take to ensure privacy of personal data of participants:

21. Do you follow written procedures for protecting privacy?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and state any corrective actions you will take:

22. Do you follow or are you aware of any official national or international guidelines on protecting privacy?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline and provide references:

23. Will you clarify to the participants that all data collected in the activities they are participating in will be kept entirely confidential and that their anonymity will be protected in full?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline and provide references:

24. Do you identify persons and their professions who are authorised to have access to the data collected and / or who have access to any data storage devices, both, paper-based and electronically?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please briefly list these persons and their professions.

F) Health and Safety (H&S)

25. Will your participants follow any specific H&S procedures /protocols /mitigation measures for the purpose of the testing?

- Yes No

In **either case**, please provide a brief outline or explanation and provide some references:

26. [Only in case vulnerable participants participate in the testing] Will vulnerable participants be provided with additional H&S procedures/protocols/mitigation measures than those offered to non-disability participants?

- Yes No

In **either case**, please explain what and / or why:

27. Will you inform the participants about the H&S procedures / protocols / measures that they need to follow/take?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and the corrective actions you will take:

G) Risk Management

28. Do you have procedures to perform risk-assessment concerning the breach of privacy and / or breach of safety?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and refer to any corrective actions you will take:

29. Is your organisation insured against risks as a result of breach of privacy and/or health and safety risks?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it and state the insurer, if possible:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and state who would cover any insurance-related costs:

30. For conducting research and manage the risk, do you need to involve other organisations (unit, division, department, etc.) which are outside of your direct supervision, the activities of which may influence the ethics/legal integrity of your research and constitute potential threats for the ethical and legal conduct of the activity you are leading?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it and describe the measures you plan to take for avoiding or mitigating these risks:

31. Where any risk assessments relevant to the Framework Directive 89/391/EEC (Health and Safety at Work) and its supporting Directives as per the precautionary principle necessary for the testing?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of these, include the location of relevant risk assessments (e.g. supporting document; link) and briefly describe the identified risks and relevant treatment measures you plan to take for these risks:

Annex II: Information sheet example template

5G-ROUTES Draft Information sheet and informed consent form

Information Sheet

[Date]

5G-ROUTES: 5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Introduction: [Briefly state who you are and explain that you are inviting them to participate in the research you are doing. Inform them that they may talk to anyone they feel comfortable talking with about the research and that they can take time to reflect on whether they want to participate or not. Assure the participant that if they do not understand some of the words or concepts, that you will take time to explain them as you go along and that they can ask questions now or later.

Example: I am X, working for the Y Research Institute. We are doing research on connected and automated mobility, which is becoming the new trend in transportation, as part the European Union-funded¹ 5G-ROUTES research project coordinated by ERICSSON EESTI AS (EEE), Estonia in partnership with [Insert NAME of your INSTITUTION²]. I am going to give you information and invite you to be part of this research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research. In case there are some words that you do not understand, please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask me about or the staff.]

Purpose of research: [Explain in lay terms why we are doing research within the framework of 5G-ROUTES project. Use local and simplified terms. The language used should clarify rather than confuse. There are guides on the internet to help you find substitutes for words which are overly scientific or are professional jargon.

Example: the purpose of this project is to conduct advanced field trials of the most representative and innovative Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) applications functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North') spanning across 3 European Union member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications [provide explanations in lay terms for 5G and 3GPP] under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe. The findings of this questionnaire / survey / interview / workshop / trial / group discussion / other (Specify:.....)³ will assist the consortium partners to capture and assess and/or validate the effectiveness of the 5G-ROUTES 5G CAM ecosystem through relevant use cases.]

Participant selection: [most applicable for vulnerable populations: State why this participant has been chosen for this research. People often wonder why they have been chosen to participate and may be fearful, confused or concerned.

Example: We are inviting people with mobility disability to participate in the research on testing new automated technologies for understanding how our proposed developments may best contribute in alleviating such impairments.]

Voluntary Participation and right to refuse or withdraw: [Indicate clearly that they can choose to participate or not. Participants with cognitive impairment, if any, will be reminded about their participation being voluntary before moving to the consent form and signing it.

Example: Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. You are free to leave at any time, change your mind later and stop participating at any time even if you agreed earlier, without any impacts on you or your future participation in the project. You are also free to refuse to answer any questions or provide any information that you do not wish to discuss. You have the right to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making any decision].

Information on the 5G-ROUTES applications and systems to be tested: [provide as much give information about the applications as is appropriate and understandable about the system and applications and explain what it does/means (including illustrations of the applications or real demos, depending on availability; participants with cognitive impairments, if any, will

¹ Grant agreement number 951867

² 5G-ROUTES partner conducting the research and innovation activity will amend all highlighted parts

³ Strike through options that do not apply.

receive information with illustrations (i.e. pictures, examples of functionalities, in simple language with no jargon.). Explain the known experience with these applications/services (mainly for technological implementations already in the market).

Example: The system and applications we are testing in this research are called A,B, X. Many of them have been tested before but now they will be integrated and tested in large field scale conditions as one system. The application (s) ABX is made by C, D, E. We know of no problem or risks related to its/their use. Some participants in the research will not be given this/these application(s) we are testing. Instead, they will be given another/other application(s) XYZ. There is no risk, other than usual traffic risk associated with the use of this/these application(s) and no known problems.]

Procedures and Protocols: [Describe or explain the exact procedures that will be followed on a step-by-step basis, the tests that will be done, data that will be gathered. Participants should know what to expect and what is expected of them. Use active, rather than conditional, language. Write "we will ask you to...." instead of "we would like to ask you to...." An illustration of the system and applications, if available, will help participants understand the process better ".]

Duration: [Include a statement about the time commitments of the research for the participant including both the duration of the research and follow-up, if relevant.

Example: The research takes place over ____ (number of) days in total. During that time, it will be necessary for you to come to the testing facility _____(number of) days , for ____ (number of) hours each day. We would like to meet with you for a final validation of the results X months after your last testing.]

Risks: [Explain and describe any possible or anticipated risks. Describe the level of care that will be available in the event that harm does occur, who will provide it, and who will pay for it (e.g. traffic-related risks). A risk can be thought of as being the likelihood that harm may occur. Provide enough information about any risks and relevant mitigation/safety measures that the participant can make an informed decision.

Example: By participating in this research it is there will be no more possibility to be at greater risk than you would otherwise be by driving in usual traffic conditions. While the possibility of this happening is very low, you should still be aware of the possibility. We will try to decrease the chances of this event occurring, but if something unexpected happens, we will provide you with_____.]

Benefits (if reimbursement is used; benefits might not be provided): [Mention only those activities that will be actual benefits and not those to which they are entitled regardless of participation. Benefits may be divided into benefits to the individual, benefits to the community in which the individual resides, and benefits to society as a whole as a result of finding an answer to the research question.

Example: Your participation in this research, is likely to help us find the answer to the research question [state] and the research community / society may benefit from the advancements in automated and connected mobility your participation may result to.].

Reimbursements: [State clearly what you will provide the participants with as a result of their participation. There is no encouragement for using incentives. However, it is recommended that reimbursements for expenses incurred as a result of participation in the research be provided. These may include, for example, travel costs and money for wages lost due to time commitment for testing. The amount should be determined within the host country context.

Example: We will give you [amount of money] to pay for your travel to the place of study taken place/follow-ups/parking and we will give you [amount] for lost work time. You will not be given any other money or gifts to take part in this research.]

Confidentiality: [Explain how the research team will maintain the confidentiality of data.

Example: We will not be sharing the identity of those participating in the research and the record of your involvement in the research will be kept confidential and no-one but the researchers will be able to see it. Any personal data you provide will be handled according to the legal requirements outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. You have been informed that everything you say will be anonymized. The event data will be recorded via [paper notes/electronic notes/voice recorder/camera recorder] and you can request a copy of these records to review if you wish. I understand that I am also allowed to delete or make any changes to these records if I feel the information I provided could be improved or clarified. I understand that information about my personal involvement in the research will be kept in a secure location at ERICSSON EESTI AS and that my information will be made anonymous when shared with 5G-ROUTES project team. I understand that the data I provide will be [anonymized, pseudonymised] and the record of my participation will be kept in a file separate from the project data. Any information about you will have a number on it instead of your name. Only the principal investigator will know what your number is and we will lock that information up with a lock and key. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except [name who will have access to the information]. I understand that the data will be kept for 3 year after the 5G-ROUTES project ends, but my personal data will be destroyed when the project ends.

Sharing of the results: [Where it is relevant, your plan for sharing the information with the participants should be provided. If you have a plan and a timeline for the sharing of information, include the details. You should also inform the participant that the research findings will be shared more broadly, for example, through publications and conferences.

Example: Confidential information will not be shared. There will be small meetings with consortium and these will be announced. After these meetings, we will publish the results in order that other interested people may learn from our research.]

Who to Contact: [Provide the name and contact information of someone who is involved, informed and accessible (a local person who can actually be contacted and of the Coordinator). State how the research has been approved.

Example: This research conforms to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This procedure has been reviewed and approved by [name of the local IRB and/or the Academic Ethics Committee of TTU], which is a committee whose task it is to make sure that research is conducted in an ethical and legal manner. If you have any questions you may ask them now or later, even after the study has started. In case you are looking for additional information/clarifications for the testing/research that has been conducted, feel free to contact ERICSSON EESTI AS (Project Coordinator: provide [name, address/telephone number/e-mail]) about any queries relating to my data or the project itself.]

Annex III: Informed consent form example template

5G-ROUTES: 5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Lead partners: *[Insert name of person/institution conducting the research activity]*

Participant Identification Number for this project:

Please ✓ box

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated <i>[insert date]</i> explaining the above research project and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is purely voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline and can contact Project Coordinator ERICSSON EESTI AS via telephone at +372 6 500 900.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my responses and personal data will be kept strictly confidential.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I give permission for members of the project team to have access to my anonymised data. I understand that my name will not be linked with the research materials, and I will not be identified or identifiable in the report or reports that result from the research.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to take part in the above research project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I received a copy of both the information sheet and the informed consent form.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Participant
(or legal representative)

Date

Signature

Name of person taking consent

Date

Signature

(if different from lead researcher) To be signed and dated in the presence of the participant

Lead researcher

Date

Signature

To be signed and dated in the presence of the participant

Copies:

Once this has been signed by all parties the participant should receive a copy of the signed and dated participant consent form, the letter/pre-written script/information sheet and any other written information provided to the participants. A copy of the signed and dated consent form should be placed in the project's main record (e.g. a site file), which must be kept in a secure location.